

Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines

Companion Guide for Anaphylaxis 2022 Updated CD

V2.0 – July 2025

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Description of the deliverable	This deliverable updates an earlier version of the Anaphylaxis (2022 Case Definition) Companion Guide (SO2, D2.5.2.1; V1.1 completed 19 Oct, 2022) as follows: new published evidence added to Background rate and Risk Factor sections; data abstraction and interpretation form along with algorithms for assessing level of diagnostic certainty amended to harmonize with those available online as part of digital transformation including a glossary of terms. This guide should replace the earlier version and can be used by stakeholders to assess the occurrence of anaphylaxis in several settings including as an adverse event following immunization.
Key words	Anaphylaxis, Brighton case definition, risk factors, background rates, ICD-9-CM, ICD-10-CM, MedDRA, SNOMED CT, case definition level of certainty.

DOCUMENT HISTORY

NAME OF DOCUMENT	DATE	VERSION	CONTRIBUTOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Anaphylaxis (2007 case definition) Companion Guide	5 February 2021	V 1.0	Barbara Law Marta Rojo Villaescusa	Final version of guide for Anaphylaxis V 1.0
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Anaphylaxis (2022 case definition) Companion Guide	5 September 2022	V 1.0	Barbara Law	Redraft of 2021 Companion Guide to include changes in the Anaphylaxis V2.0 case definition
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Anaphylaxis V-2 Companion Guide	10 September 2022	V 1.0	Mike Gold Wan-Ting Huang	Review and comments
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Anaphylaxis V-2 Companion Guide	19 October 2022	V 1.1	Barbara Law	Finalization of the document
SPEAC 2 D2.4.1	July 2025	V2.0	Barbara Law Hammad Ali Marta Rojo Villaescusa Ariel Zadok Dale Nordenberg Wan-Ting Huang	Updated Background Rate and Risk Factor Sections based on scoping literature review Updated case report forms and algorithms to the latest versions developed as part of digital transformation
SPEAC 2 D2.5.2.1	18 August 2025	V2.0	Preetha Iyengar	EB review
SPEAC 2 D2.5.2.1	31 August 2025	V2.0	Andy Stergachis	EB review

DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

ABC	Automated Brighton Classification
AEFI	Adverse Events Following Immunization
AESI	Adverse Events of Special Interest
Alpha-gal	Galactose alpha 1,2-galactose
APDC	Australian Pacific Data Centers
ASCIA	Australian Society of Clinical Immunology and Allergy
BCCD	Brighton Collaboration Case Definition
BC	Brighton Collaboration
BCG	Bacille Calmette-Guerin
BP	Blood pressure
CD	Case Definition
CEPI	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness and Innovation
CG	Companion guide
CI	Confidence interval
CIOMS	Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
CISSS	China Immunization Safety Surveillance System
CUI	Concept Unique Identifier
CVMS	COVID-19 Vaccination Management System
D, d	Diphtheria toxoid; D is a higher concentration for use in pediatric vaccines; d a lower concentrations for vaccines used for older children (≥ 7 years) and adults
DTaP	Diphtheria, tetanus, and acellular pertussis
DTaP-IPV-Hib	Diphtheria, tetanus, acellular pertussis, inactivated poliovirus, and Haemophilus influenzae type b combination vaccine
DTaP-IPV-Hib-HBV	A combined vaccine that protects against diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis (whooping cough), polio, Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib), and hepatitis B
DTwP-Hib	A combination vaccine that protects against diphtheria, tetanus, whooping cough (pertussis), and Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib) infections
EAACI	European Academy of Allergy and Clinical Immunology
ED	Emergency Department
EDDC	Experimental Drug Development Centre
FAAN	Food Allergy and Anaphylaxis Network
GPRD	General Practice Research Database
HBV	Hepatitis B vaccine
HES	Hospital Episodes Statistics
Hib	<i>Haemophilus influenzae type b</i>
HMO	Health Maintenance Organization
HPV, HPV4, HPV9	Human papillomavirus; 4 or 9 indicate vaccines with 4 (quadrivalent) or 9 (nonavalent) different HPV strains
IC	Information Component
ICD-CM	International Classification of Diseases – Clinical Modification
ICD-CA	International Classification of Diseases – Canada
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
IIV	Inactivated influenza vaccine

IIV3-Adj, IIVD4-SD, IIV4-HD, IIV4-cc	Inactivated influenza vaccine variants, IIV – trivalent adjuvanted, IIV-quadrivalent – standard dose, IIV – quadrivalent high dose, IIV – quadrivalent cell based
IPV	Inactivated polio vaccine
IQRJEV	Interquartile range; specifically the difference between the data set 3 rd (75 percentile) and first (25 th percentile) quartiles; represents a measure of the spread of the middle 50% of values
KDCA	Korea Disease Control and Prevention Agency
LAIV	Live attenuate influenza vaccine
lang	language
LOC	Level of diagnostic certainty (of BCCD)
MBDS	Minimum Basic Data Set
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
MI	Milliliter
mm Hg	Millimeters of mercury (unit for blood pressure measurements)
MM	Measles Mumps vaccine
MMR	Measles Mumps Rubella vaccine
MMRV	Measles Mumps Rubella Varicella vaccine
MR	Measles Rubella vaccine
mRNA	messenger RNA
NASS	National AEFI Surveillance System
ng	nanogram
NIAID/FAAN	National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Disease / Food Allergy and Anaphylaxis Network
Noexp	No explosion (syntax used in pubmed searches); instruction to not include or search narrower terms
OHCA	Out of hospital cardiac arrest
OPD	Outpatient department
OR	Odds ratio
P, aP, ap	Pertussis (whooping cough) vaccine antigens: P refers to the antigen derived from whole <i>Bordetella pertussis</i> bacterial cells; aP refers to the ‘acellular’ antigen used for immunizing infants and children aged <7 years; ap is also ‘acellular’ antigen, but indicates a lower concentration, used in vaccines for older children and adults.
PCV7/10/13	Pneumococcal conjugate vaccine; number 7, 10 or 13 refer to the number of unique pneumococcal serotypes in the vaccine
PDAT	Publication date (pubmed search term)
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PEI	Paul Ehrlich Institute
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PPS23	Pneumococcal polysaccharide vaccine with 23 unique pneumococcal serotypes
ptyp	Publication type (pubmed search term)
ROK	Republic of Korea
ROR	Reporting Odds Ratio
SD	Standard deviation
SNOMEDCT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine -- Clinical Terms
SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines
Tt	Tetanus toxoid
TB	Tuberculosis

TBE	Tick-borne encephalitis
Tdap	Tetanus, diphtheria and acellular pertussis vaccine
THIN	The Health Improvement Network
tiab	Title-abstract (pubmed search term)
TIV	Trivalent Inactivated Influenza Vaccine
TIV-ID	Trivalent Inactivated Influenza Vaccine – Intradermal
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
VZV	Varicella Zoster Virus
WAO	World Allergy Organization
WP2	Work Package 2
YF	Yellow Fever
yrs	years

INTRODUCTION

1. Background

CEPI has contracted with the Brighton Collaboration (BC), through the Task Force for Global Health, to harmonize the safety assessment of CEPI-funded vaccines via its Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines (SPEAC) Project.

A key aspect of this harmonization has been creation of lists of priority potential adverse events of special interest (AESI) that are relevant to vaccines targeting CEPI target diseases.

SPEAC Work Package 2 created resources and tools for the AESI including:

1. Tabular summaries of risk factors and background rates for each AESI.
2. Guidance on AESI real time investigation, data collection, analysis and presentation.
3. Spreadsheet summaries of ICD9/10, and MedDRA codes for each AESI.
4. Tools to facilitate capturing the specific clinical data needed to meet AESI case definitions across a variety of settings applicable to clinical trials, epidemiologic studies and individual case causality assessment. These include:
 - a. Data abstraction and interpretation forms to facilitate capturing data relevant to the Brighton case definition.
 - b. Rules for creating new variables relevant to the case definition criteria, if needed.
 - c. Tabular formulae for determining Brighton Level of Diagnostic Certainty (LOC) based on the final value of each case definition criterion (YES, NO or UNKNOWN).
 - d. Pictorial algorithm showing the path to each LOC (1-5) based on criterion values. This contains all the information needed to determine LOC and thus can be used as a standalone tool.
 - e. Glossary of terms relevant to the case definition.

Initially these resources and tools were developed as separate documents but starting in 2020 they were pulled together into a single 'Companion Guide (CG)' for each published Brighton Collaboration Case Definition. The first CGuide for the 2007 Anaphylaxis case definition[1] was finalized Feb 5, 2021. An updated guide was released Oct 19, 2022 to accompany a revised case definition for Anaphylaxis[2] which was first published online Nov 24, 2022 and in print version in 2023.

In November 2022, SPEAC began a new contract with CEPI as SPEAC 2.0. A key feature was to embark on Digital Transformation of tools and resources developed as part of the original SPEAC project from 2019 through October 2022. The original data abstraction forms, tabular checklist and level of certainty algorithms published in CG V1.0 that accompanied the 2007 Anaphylaxis case definition (CD) [1] and CG V1.1 that accompanied the 2022 revised CD[2] have been revised as part of the digital transformation process. Another initiative of SPEAC 2.0 was to extend and update the background rate and risk factor sections (which were the same for CG V1.0 and V1.1), based on a more thorough literature review than was done for the first versions of the Guides.

V1.1 of the Anaphylaxis companion guide for the 2022 revised case definition included a section that outlined the changes in the updated CD versus the 2007 version. For brevity these are not repeated in this main section but can be found in Appendix 7.

2. Objective of this deliverable

To update the previously completed Companion Guide to the 2022 Brighton case definition for Anaphylaxis[1] to 1) add new published evidence on background incidence and risk factors; and 2) update the data abstraction forms and

algorithms so they match what are being used for Digital Transformation including the Automated Brighton Classification (ABC Tool) and other digital data collection tools.

3. Methods

The methods for developing each of the tools are briefly described in Appendix 6 of this Guide along with links to source documents which have more detailed methodology. More detail regarding the literature review done to capture newly published evidence on anaphylaxis background incidence and risk factors as well as a new section related to all published evidence on vaccine – anaphylaxis associations is presented below.

A scoping literature review was done using two different search strategies.

The search strategy to update the background incidence and risk factor section from the previous guide was as follows:

```
("Anaphylaxis"[Mesh] OR "anaphylaxis"[tiab] OR "anaphylactic"[tiab])
AND ("Incidence"[Mesh:noexp] OR "incidence*"[tiab] OR "attack rate*"[tiab] OR "person time rate*"[tiab] OR
"background rate*"[tiab] OR "Epidemiology"[Mesh:noexp] OR "epidemiology"[tiab] OR "etiology"[Subheading] OR
"etiology"[tiab] OR "pathogenesis"[tiab] OR "causes"[tiab] OR "causality"[tiab] OR "Risk Factors"[Mesh] OR "risk
factor*"[tiab] OR "population at risk"[tiab] OR "populations at risk"[tiab] OR "risk score*"[tiab] OR "health
correlate*"[tiab])
AND ("2006/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])
AND English[lang]
AND ("Meta-Analysis"[ptyp] OR "Systematic Review"[ptyp] OR "Review"[ptyp] OR "Observational Study"[ptyp])
NOT ("animals"[Mesh] NOT "humans"[Mesh])
```

The search strategy to identify articles looking at evidence for vaccine association with anaphylaxis was as follows:

```
("Vaccines"[Mesh] OR "vaccine"[tiab] OR "vaccines"[tiab] OR "Vaccination"[Mesh] OR "vaccination"[tiab] OR
"vaccinations"[tiab] OR "vaccinate"[tiab] OR "vaccinated"[tiab] OR "Immunization"[Mesh] OR "immunization"[tiab] OR
"immunizations"[tiab] OR "immunisation"[tiab] OR "immunisations"[tiab] OR "immunize"[tiab] OR "immunized"[tiab] OR
"immunise"[tiab] OR "immunised"[tiab])
AND ("Anaphylaxis"[Mesh] OR "anaphylaxis"[tiab] OR "anaphylactic"[tiab])
AND ("2006/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])
AND English[lang]
NOT (Comment[ptyp] OR Editorial[ptyp] OR Letter[ptyp] OR News[ptyp] OR Newspaper Article[ptyp])
NOT ("animals"[Mesh] NOT "humans"[Mesh])
```

The ‘background incidence and risk factor’ and ‘vaccine association’ searches were conducted on 19 July 2024. The results of each search were uploaded into separate COVIDENCE files. Two investigators (BL, HA) screened by title/abstract first. Any conflicts were resolved to reach consensus on the final list for full text review which was done by a single investigator (BL). Additional articles were found via hand search of the included articles citation lists.

All articles related to background incidence were further screened by one investigator (MRV) to identify articles that had original incidence data. Citations included in all reviews and meta-analyses were obtained to ensure only original data would

be captured. A standard excel spreadsheet was used to extract the incidence data. Subsequently the excel file was reviewed by a different investigator (BL) before updating the background incidence table. All articles included for background incidence were reviewed (BL) to capture key methodological details for presentation in a separate table.

Data extraction for all articles related to general risk factors (not including vaccine as a risk factor) was done by one investigator (BL) using a word document to capture key findings.

Data extraction for all articles related to possible or proven vaccine-associations was done by EpiCare Consulting LLC using a formatted excel spreadsheet created by WP2 (HA, BL). The extracted data were reviewed by one WP2 investigator (HA) and summary tables prepared for presentation in the Guide.

PRISMA summaries for each of the two literature reviews were prepared.

4. Results.

Both search strategies were run on 19 July 2024 (MD). Figures 1 and 2 show the literature search results for incidence/non-vaccine risk factors and vaccine risk factors respectively, following PRISMA guidelines[1].

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram for articles retrieved for incidence and non-vaccine risk factors.

Figure 2. PRISMA diagram for articles retrieved for vaccine-related risk factors.

Table 1. Summary of the changes from V1 to V2 of the Anaphylaxis (2022 CD) Companion Guide

Change category	Guide Version 1 (V1.0/V1.1)	Guide Version 2 (V2.0)
Additional glossary terms defined: bilateral, cyanosis, hereditary angioedema, hypoxia, new onset, persistent and vasovagal.		
Order and content of Appendices	Appendix 1. Risk Factors Appendix 2. Background rates Appendix 3. Medical codes Appendix 4. CD Key caveats Appendix 5. Data abstraction and interpretation forms with LOC algorithms and glossary of terms	Appendix 1. Medical codes Appendix 3. Risk Factors Same numbering and order for the rest.
Medical codes		No changes
Background incidence	Incidence provided from 24 studies: 6 USA, 1 Chile, 1 China, 1 Korea, 3 Australia, 4 UK, 1 Switzerland, 2 Denmark, 1 Finland, 1 Sweden, 2 Spain, 1 Italy, and 1 multiple European countries (ADVANCE)	Table 2.1 has an additional 22 studies with incidence data from: 1 Canada, 3 USA, 1 China, 1 Singapore, 5 Australia, 2 Denmark, 1 France, 1 Germany, 1 Italy, 1 Turkiye, 2 UK, 1 Israel, 1 multiple European Countries (ACCESS), 1 multiple global regions – Europe, Japan and USA. 2 new tables added: Table 2.2 details methodology used for all incidence studies, including those in V1.0/1.1 Guides; Table 2.3 provides details regarding case definitions used for specific studies.
Risk Factors	1 Table of Risk factors presenting evidence related to: Age, Gender, Genetics, Geography, Comorbidities, Medication and Vaccine.	3 separate tables created: Table 3.1 Anaphylaxis triggers including food, drugs, vaccines, insect venom, physical factors, inhaled allergens, contact allergens, infection and idiopathic anaphylaxis; Table 3.2 presents risk factors for increased incidence of anaphylaxis (age, gender, genetics, geography, comorbidities); Table 3.3 presents risk factors for increased severity of anaphylaxis (age, gender, genetics, comorbidity, medication, physical factors and in a separate row, associations with fatal anaphylaxis). An additional 7 new tables provide evidence for vaccine-anaphylaxis association including: measles containing, COVID-19, influenza, HPV, pneumococcal, yellow fever and miscellaneous other vaccines.

Key Caveats for diagnosis, data analysis and presentation		No changes
Data collection form	<p>Table 2 for data collection form (Step 1)</p> <p>Table 3. to define additional criterion values.</p>	<p>Updated to match the simplified digital version of the form with the following changes from V1.0: Table 2 now identified as Step 1 only. All data entry answers now needed for each major or minor criterion using Yes, No or Unknown, which are defined at the beginning of Step 1. Any terms defined in the glossary now yellow highlighted in the data form.</p> <p>Table 3 now identified as Step 2 and expanded using the Yes, No or Unknown answers from Step 1 to define all the Major and Minor criteria. The Minor respiratory criterion is now D2 not D3.</p>
4. CD criterion values	Table 4 provided to summarize all criterion values (Y=YES, N=NO, U=UNKNOWN) from the data collection Tables 2 and 3.	Same as in V1.0 but now labelled as Step 3 rather than Table 4.
5. Level of Certainty (LOC) Logic	<p>Table 5: Tabular algorithm with logic (formulae) to determine LOC based on criterion values in the summary table.</p> <p>2 paths defined to reach LOC3</p>	<p>Now labelled as Step 4 rather than a numbered table.</p> <p>Now 3 paths defined to reach LOC3. Two the same as in V1.0 but added the scenario where there is a skin major and a respiratory minor but all others are No or unknown.</p>
6. Pictorial Level of Certainty Algorithm	Stand alone 1 page figure with all information to assign level of diagnostic certainty. Error in the pathway logic for LOC2: said to be (C or D-1 or E or F = YES) but should have been ≥ 2 of (C, D-1, E or F) = YES	Similar stand alone 1 page figure with all information to assign level of diagnostic certainty. Logic error in the pathway corrected.
7. Glossary of Terms	Provided as Table 6	Several new terms defined: bilateral, cyanosis, hereditary angioedema, hypoxia, new onset, persistent, vasovagal

The outputs are provided as separate appendices to simplify printing as needed. These are provided as appendices shown below.

1. Anaphylaxis Diagnostic Codes: ICD-9CM, ICD-10CM, MedDRA, SNOMEDCT
2. Anaphylaxis Background Rates

3. Anaphylaxis Risk Factors
4. Anaphylaxis case definition key caveats for diagnosis, data analysis and presentation
5. Anaphylaxis data abstraction and interpretation forms with algorithms for assessing level of certainty and glossary of terms.
6. Summary of methods. Also provides links, as appropriate, to the original deliverable documents with more detailed methodology.

5. Recommendations & discussion.

This guide brings together many resources and tools related to the AESI of anaphylaxis (2022 updated case definition), several of which have been updated based on a scoping literature review. These include: ICD-9/10-CM SNOMEDCT and MedDRA codes for data entry or database searching; updated section on background rates; updated section on risk factors, in particular evidence for vaccine-anaphylaxis association; guidance for real time investigation; a simplified data abstraction form and algorithms for assigning level of diagnostic certainty that matches what is available in the online ABC tool and redcap forms; and a glossary of terms for thrombocytopenia.

SPEAC recommends that the tools be used in order to assign level of certainty for all identified AEFI with features of anaphylaxis. This standard, harmonized approach will facilitate signal detection and assessment as well as the capacity to combine data across trials for meta-analyses.

APPENDIX 1.

Anaphylaxis Diagnostic Codes: ICD-9/10-CM, MedDRA and SNOMEDCT

1.1 Anaphylaxis Diagnostic Codes: MedDRA, ICD-9/10-CM and SNOMEDCT

All codes in the table were derived from codemapper as described in Appendix 6.[3-7]

TABLE 1.1 NARROW TERMS FOR ANAPHYLAXIS

UMLS Concept		Diagnostic Coding System Term and Codes				
CUI	Name	Term	MedDRA	ICD-9-CM	ICD-10-CM	SNOMEDCT-US
C5549840	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product					471351000124102
C0857035	Acute anaphylaxis	Acute anaphylaxis	10000664100006			
		Acute anaphyl	6210000663			
		Acute anaphylactic reaction				
C0002792	Anaphylaxis	Anaphylactic reaction	10002198			
		Anaphylactic shock	10002199	999.49	T78.2	87467006
		Anaphylaxis	10002218			39579001
		Systemic anaphylactic reaction	10042930			
		Systemic anaphylaxis	10042931			157755003
		Allergic shock	10069526		T78.2	
C3161335	Other anaphylactic reaction			995.0		
C0429892	Type 1 hypersensitivity response					12263007
C0340865	Anaphylactoid reaction					35001004
C0161840	Anaphylactic transfusion reaction		10067113			79337003
C3263932	Anaphylactic reaction due to adverse effect of correct drug or medicament properly administered				T88.6	
C3263869	Anaphylaxis due to serum				T80.5	
C2349793	Anaphylactic reaction due to serum				T80.5	
C3161457	Anaphylactoid reaction due to serum				T80.5	
C3263868	Allergic shock due to serum				T80.5	213320003
C0020523	Immediate hypersensitivity	Immediate hypersensitivity	10021413			20671006
		Immediate hypersensitivity reaction	10021414			
		Hypersensitivity type 1	10020762			
		Hypersensitivity type 1 NOS	10020763			
		IgE-mediated allergic disorder				422076005
C4316895	Anaphylactic shock					735173007

C0274304	Anaphylactic shock, due to adverse effect of correct medicinal substance properly administered	Anaphylactic shock due to adverse effect of correct drug or medicament properly administered		T88.6	212995001
		Anaphylactic shock due to serum		T80.5	213320003
		Allergic shock, due to adverse effect of correct medicinal substance properly administered			111737003
		Anaphylactic shock, due to adverse effect of correct medicinal substance properly administered			419042001
C2886701	Anaphylactic shock, unspecified, initial encounter			T78.2XXA	
C2886702	Anaphylactic shock, unspecified, subsequent encounter			T78.2XXD	
C2886703	Anaphylactic shock, unspecified, sequelae			T78.2XXS	
C0391985	Anaphylactic shock, not elsewhere classified	10002212			
C3494642	Anaphylaxis caused by human papillomavirus vaccine				428241000124101
C3494646	Anaphylactic reaction caused by diphtheria and tetanus vaccine				428281000124107
C3494647	Anaphylaxis caused by tetanus, diphtheria and acellular pertussis vaccine				428291000124105
C3494648	Anaphylaxis caused by meningococcal vaccine				428301000124106
C3494649	Anaphylaxis due to Hepatitis B vaccine				428321000124101
C3494650	Anaphylaxis caused by rotavirus vaccine				428331000124103
C3536632	Anaphylaxis due to Hemophilus influenzae type b vaccine				433621000124101
C5549835	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing Streptococcus pneumoniae antigen				471141000124102
C5549836	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing Hepatitis A virus antigen				471311000124103
C5549837	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing human poliovirus antigen				471321000124106

C5549838	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing Measles morbillivirus and Mumps orthorubulavirus and Rubella virus antigens					471331000124109
C5549839	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing Human alphaherpesvirus 3 antigens					471341000124104
C5549841	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing influenza virus antigen					471361000124100
C5549842	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing alphaherpesvirus 3 recombinant surface glycoprotein E antigen					471371000124107
C5549843	Anaphylaxis caused by vaccine product containing live attenuated human alphaherpesvirus 3 antigens					471381000124105
C0685898	Food anaphylaxis	Anaphylactic reaction due to food	10054843	995.6	T78.0	91941002
		Anaphylactic reaction to food				
		Food anaphylaxis				
		Anaphylactic reaction due to adverse food reaction				
		Anaphylactic shock due to adverse food reaction	10002200			
		Food-induced anaphylactoid reaction				212994002 241946006
C1304184	Anaphylaxis due to ingested food					40239008
C0344159	Anaphylaxis caused by venom		10073013			241930003
C4543744	Anaphylaxis caused by insect venom		C			735447008
C1304185	Anaphylaxis caused by bite and/or sting					402391007
C5397548	Anaphylaxis caused by insect bite and/or insect sting					871926004
C2315598	Anaphylaxis due to hymenoptera venom					430980000
C0344160	Bee sting-induced anaphylaxis					241931004
C0344161	Wasp sting-induced anaphylaxis					24193006
C0344164	Peanut-induced anaphylaxis					241933001
C0344166	Egg white-induced anaphylaxis					241935008
C1998391	Anaphylaxis due to fish					427903006
C0344165	Seafood-induced anaphylaxis					241934007

C0859880	Anaphylactic shock due to milk products	Anaphylactic shock due to milk products Anaphylactic reaction due to milk products	10002206	995.67		
C0344167	Cow's milk protein-induced anaphylaxis					241936009
C1998404	Anaphylaxis due to fruit					429751004
C2711329	Anaphylaxis due to tree nut					441495001
C1997442	Anaphylaxis due to vegetable					428795003
C2711964	Anaphylaxis due to seed					441492003
C1997452	Anaphylaxis due to mollusk					427833000
C2063647	Anaphylaxis due to shellfish					442052005
C0344178	Non-allergic anaphylaxis caused by drug					241947002
C3697499	Non-allergic anaphylaxis caused by food additive					
C1562287	Anaphylaxis due to substance					417516000
C5397207	Blood product-induced anapylactoid reaction					871554001
C2064633	Anaphylactic reaction to latex	Anaphylaxis caused by latex				441593005
C4543745	Anaphylaxis due to mast cell disorder					7354480003
C4544077	Shock co-occurrent and due to anaphylaxis caused by serum					735955001
C4546212	Anaphylaxis caused by low temperature					762455001
C0859860	Anaphylactic shock due to milk products		10002206	995.67		
C0344168	Drug-induced anaphylaxis					241937000
C0344169	Penicillin-induced anaphylaxis					241938005
C0344170	Insulin-induced anaphylaxis					241930002
C0344183	Exercise anaphylaxis	Exercise anaphylaxis Exercise-induced anaphylaxis	10060689			241952007
C5546138	Food-dependent exercise-induced anaphylaxis					1144980001
C1096621	Anaphylactic reaction to chemical		10054845			
C4274489	Anaphylaxis caused by sulfite salt					71588704
C4305004	Anaphylaxis caused by lupin flour					71904004
C4305609	Anaphylaxis caused by sulfur dioxide					716374005

C5547723	Non-allergic anaphylaxis caused by organic phosphorus compound				1155989002
C5547724	Non-allergic anaphylaxis caused by parasympathomimetic agent				1155990006
C1960690	Immune hypersensitivity disorder by mechanism				427439005
C5438739	Anaphylaxis due to Hevea brasiliensis latex protein				1003758002
C0344171	Human protein-induced anaphylaxis				241940000
C0344173	Aeroallergen-induced anaphylaxis				241942008
C1298697	Anaphylactic urticaria				373674001
C0413235	Idiopathic anaphylaxis				241954008
C0812176	Anaphylaxis management				386512002
C0854649	Anaphylaxis treatment	10002222			
C4545321	Anaphylaxis care				737855007

1.2 Anaphylaxis Diagnostic Codes: ICD-11

ICD-11 was released by WHO in February 2025 and the English browser is available here: <https://icd.who.int/browse/2025-01/mms/en>. In the absence of concept mapping by codemapper, new ICD-11 codes are not contained in Tables 1.1. Nevertheless, given the high degree of relevance for specificity of coding Anaphylaxis, they are presented below:

Under 04 Diseases of the immune system, is a section for allergic or hypersensitivity conditions which includes:

- 4A80 Allergic or hypersensitivity disorders involving the respiratory tract
- 4A81 Allergic or hypersensitivity disorders involving the eye
- 4A82 Allergic or hypersensitivity disorders involving skin or mucous membranes
- 4A83 Allergic or hypersensitivity disorders involving the gastrointestinal tract
- 4A84 Anaphylaxis: see below for specific codes and other changes related to anaphylaxis
- 4A85 Complex allergic or hypersensitivity conditions

Two major changes from ICD-10 relates to codes for anaphylaxis:

- Multiple categories specific for cause are now gathered under the Anaphylaxis section (4A84)
 - 4A84.0 Anaphylaxis due to allergic reaction to food
 - 4A84.1 Drug-induced anaphylaxis
 - 4A84.2 Anaphylaxis due to insect venom
 - 4A84.3 Anaphylaxis provoked b physical factors
 - 4A84.30 Exercise-induced anaphylaxis
 - 4A84.31 Cold-induced anaphylaxis
 - 4A84.3Y Anaphylaxis provoked by other specified physical factors
 - 4A84.3Z Anaphylaxis provoked by unspecified physical factors
 - 4A84.4 Anaphylaxis due to inhaled allergens
 - 4A84.5 Anaphylaxis due to contact with allergens
 - 4A84.6 Anaphylaxis provoked by other specified physical factors
 - 4A84.Y other specified anaphylaxis
 - 4A84.Z Anaphylaxis, unspecified
- Extension Codes for severity have been added
 - XX09 Anaphylaxis grade 1: single organ system involved
 - XS59 Anaphylaxis grade 2: >1 organ system involved but not life-threatening
 - XS2Y Anaphylaxis grade 3: >1 organ system involved and is life-threatening
 - XS85 Anaphylaxis grade 4: Life-threatening cases with cardiac arrest

APPENDIX 2.

Anaphylaxis Background Rates

2.1 Anaphylaxis Background Rates

TABLE 1. ANAPHYLAXIS BACKGROUND RATES. See Table 2.2 for methodologic details of each of the studies below.

All types of anaphylaxes.

Country	Study years	Population (Age in years)	Incidence rate per 100,000 person years [95% confidence interval] (total cases)		
			All	Males	Females
AMERICAs					
Canada(Ontario)[8]	2015	All ages	25.0 [24.2-25.8]	22.3 [21.2- 23.4]	27.6 [26.4-28.9]
	2016	All ages	26.9 [26.0- 27.8]	23.9 [22.8- 25.1]	29.8 [28.5-31.1]
	2017	All ages	29.3 [28.4- 30.2]	25.3 [24.1- 26.5]	33.2 [31.9- 34.6]
	2018	All ages	30.4 [29.5- 31.3]	26.0 [24.8- 27.2]	34.6 [33.2- 36.0]
	2019	0–4	45.0 [40.2- 50.1]	57.3 [49.9- 65.6]	31.9 [26.3- 38.4]
		5–11	35.6 [32.2- 39.4]	43.4 [38.1- 49.3]	27.6 [23.3- 32.4]
		12–15	40.7 [35.9- 46.0]	38.4 [31.9-45.8]	43.1 [36.1- 51.1]
		16–19	51.9 [46.7- 57.6]	41.9 [35.5-49.2]	62.5 [54.4- 71.5]
		20–24	44.4 [40.4-48.6]	32.7 [28.1-37.9]	57.1 [50.6- 64.2]
		25–29	39.5 [35.8- 43.5]	27.1 [22.9- 31.8]	52.7 [46.6- 59.5]
		20-29	34.6 [32.1- 37.3]	NA	NA
		30–39	31.3 [28.8- 33.9]	26.1 [23.0- 29.5]	43.2 [39.2- 47.5]
		40–49	27.9 [25.7- 30.3]	20.7 [17.8- 23.9]	41.3 [37.4- 45.6]
		50–59	21.1 [19.0- 23.4]	23.0 [20.2- 26.1]	32.7 [29.4- 36.4]
		60–69	17.0 [14.6- 19.6]	18.7 [15.9-21.9]	23.3 [20.2- 26.7]
70–79	10.8 [8.37- 13.6]	14.6 [11.4-18.3]	19.1 [15.7- 23.0]		
≥80	32.0 [31.1-32.9]	9.34 [5.99- 13.9]	11.7 [8.54- 15.7]		
All ages	32.0 [31.1-32.9]	27.6 [26.4-28.8]	36.4 [35.0- 37.8]		
2020	All ages	26.8 [26.0- 27.6]	22.8 [21.8- 24.0]	30.6 [29.4, 31.9]	
2015–2019 Narrow definition	All ages	23.7 [23.3-24.0]			
2015–2019	All ages	28.8 [28.4-29.2]			
USA (Minnesota – Olmsted County)[9]	1983-1987	All ages	21 [17-25] (133)		
USA (Minnesota –	2001-2010	All ages	42 [38.7-45.3] (631)		

Olmsted County)[10] <i>Note: Rates are available for each year of the study in the Anaphylaxis Background Rate Spreadsheet.</i>					
USA (Minnesota)[11]	1990-2000	0-9	75.1	89.6	59.6
		10-19	65.2	63.4	67.0
		20-29	38.8	29.8	47.0
		30-39	53.3	40.3	66.1
		40-49	49.1	44.7	53.3
		50-59	40.4	24.6	54.9
		80+	28.0	24.7	30.1
		All ages	49.8[45.0-54.5] (211)	45.6[39.0-52.1] (93)	53.7[46.7-60.6] (118)
USA (Washington)[12]	1991-1997	0-4	9.9		
		5-9	7.4		
		10-14	11.2		
		15-17	14.5		
		0-17	10.5 (67)	12.2 [8.7-16.6] (40)	8.7 [5.7-12.6] (27)
USA(National)[13]	2008	0-18	10.1		
	2014	0-18	24.9		
USA (New York)[14]	1990	All ages	1.0		
	2006		4.7		
USA[15]	2005 – 2006	0-4		8.2 [6.5-9.9]	6.2[4.7-7.7]
		5-14		5.9[4.9-6.9]	5.3[4.4-6.3]
		15-24		6.2 [5.2-7.2]	10.4[9.11-11.7]
		25-34		6.7 [5.6-7.8]	10.9[9.5-12.2]
		35-44		7.6 [6.5-8.6]	9.9[8.7-11.1]
		45-54		6.6 [5.5-7.6]	10.7[9.5-12]
		55-64		6.8 [5.6-7.9]	7.8[6.6-9.0]
		65-74		6.7 [5.3-8.0]	8.0[6.6-9.4]
		75-84		5.0 [3.7-6.4]	4.7[3.6-5.9]
		85+		3.2 [1.2-5.2]	4.0[2.3-5.7]
		All ages		6.6 [2.8-10.4]	8.7[4.3-13.0]
USA[16]	2008		307.9	278.6	336.1

	2009		308.4	276.1	338.3
	2010		315.4	284.6	344.6
	2011	All ages	309.9	282.3	336.2
	2012		328.7	291.1	364.0
	2008-2012		314.2	282.6	344.0
USA[17]	2005	0-4	18.8		
		5-17	11.9		
		18-34	13.2		
		35-64	14.9		
		≥65	15.1		
		All ages	14.2		
	2006	All ages	15.7		
	2007	All ages	17.6		
	2008	All ages	18.9		
	2009	All ages	21.1		
	2010	All ages	22.7		
	2011	All ages	25.0		
	2012	All ages	27.7		
	2013	All ages	28.3		
	2014	0-4	43.2		
		5-17	35.2		
		18-34	26.1		
35-64		24.4			
≥65		34.8			
All ages		28.6	25.3	31.9	

Chile[18]	2001-2010	0-9	0.6 [0.5-0.7] (166)	1.3 [1.2-1.4] (1093)	1.5 [1.4-1.6] (1223)
		10-19	1 [0.9-1.1] (294)		
		20-29	1.1 [1.0-1.2] (278)		
		30-39	1.4 [1.3-1.6] (347)		
		40-49	1.7 [1.5-1.8] (382)		
		50-59	2.3 [2.1-2.6] (374)		
		60-69	2.4 [2.2-2.8] (254)		
		70-79	2.6 [2.2-3.0] (158)		
		80-99	2.4 [1.9-3.0] (63)		
		All ages	1.41[1.36-1.47] (2316)		
ASIA					
China (Hong Kong)[19]	1997-2007	<18	1.5[1-3]		
China (Hong Kong)[20]	2001-2	0-18 years	2.46 [1.76-3.42] (35)		
	2002/3		1.23 (17)		
	2003/4		1.85 (25)		
	2004/5		2.43 (32)		
	2005/6		1.86 (24)		
	2006/7		1.57 (20)		
	2007/8		2.96 (37)		
	2008/9		2.64 (32)		
	2009/10		3.03 (36)		
	2010/11		3.01 (35)		
	2011/12		2.61 (30)		
	2012/13		2.95 (33)		
	2013/14		4.59 (51)		
2014/15	6.63 [5.27-8.32] (74)				
Korea[21]	2008-2014	All ages	22.01 (76)	23.85	20.06
	2008	0-19	6.03 (7716)	17.54 (4261)	14.48 (3455)
		20-39	12.27 (684)		
		40-69	15.35(4456)		
		≥70	14.73(652)		
	All ages	16.02 (7716)			
2009	0-19	7.61(860)			
	20-39	13.19 (2043)			

		40-69	25.67(5108)		
		≥70	20.66 (702)		
		All ages	17.9 (8703)	19.73 (4836)	16.04 (3867)
	2010	0-19	11.56 (1288)		
		20-39	14.64 (2230)		
		40-69	17.38 (5219)		
		≥70	13.69 (768)		
		All ages	19.42 (9496)	N/A (5101)	18.12 (4395)
	2011	0-19	11.14 (1221)		
		20-39	14.76 (2219)		
		40-69	17.82 (5443)		
		≥70	15.97 (819)		
		All ages	19.65 (9687)	20.7 (5140)	18.58 (4395)
	2012	0-19	12.26(1320)		
		20-39	17.27(2570)		
		40-69	32.08(6687)		
		≥70	26.59(1025)		
		All ages	23.31 (11578)	25.35 (6333)	21.26 (5245)
	2013	0-19	16.19(1706)		
		20-39	18.89(2784)		
		40-69	22.37(7045)		
		≥70	16.57(1039)		
		All ages	25.09 (12540)	27.04 (6799)	23.1 (5741)
	2014	0-19	21.26(2189)		
		20-39	24.23(24.23)		
		40-69	28.47(28.47)		
		≥70	24.49(24.49)		
		All ages	32.19 (16198)	35.41 (8958)	28.93 (7249)
Singapore[22]	2005–2009	≤18	2.5 (108)		
AUSTRALIA/OCEANIA					
Australia[23]	1995-2000	All ages	9.9 (179)		
Australia[24]	1993-1994	0-4	4.1		
		All ages	3.7		

	2004-2005	0-4 All ages	19.7 10.8		
Australia[25]	1993-1994	0-4 All ages	3.93 3.62		
	2004-2005	0-4 All ages	19.38 8.03		
Australia[26]	2002-2007	0-4 5-14 15-24 25-64 ≥65	22.3 7.8 10.9 10.2 8.8		
Australia[27]	2005-2006	0-4 5-14 15-29 ≥30 All ages	26.4 9.0 12.4 11.3 12.2		
	2011-2012	0-4 5-14 15-29 ≥30 All ages	35.1 17.8 18.8 15.4 17.7		
Australia[28]	1997 2013	All ages All ages	5.0 19.2		
Australia[29]	2008-2009	<1 1-4 5-11 12-16 All (0-16)	2.8 18.4 9.5 11.8 11.8		
	2015-2016	<1 1-4 5-11 12-16 All (0-16)	53.5 48.2 29.2 42.2 38.7		

Australia[30]	2017-2018	All ages Narrow definition	91.3[89.2-93.4]		
		All ages Broad definition	119.5[117.1-121.9]		
EUROPE					
Denmark[31]	1973-1985	All ages	3.2 [1.9-4.9] (20)		
Denmark[32]	1995-2012	All ages	6.46[6.31-6.62] (6707)		
Denmark[33]	1994-2010 Danish-born	All ages	10.49 [9.85-11.18] (955)	9.83[8.92-10.82] (411)	11.06[10.17-12.03] (544)
Denmark[34]	2013-2014	0-17 ≥18	26.8[14.3-45.8] (13) 40.4[[32.8-49.3] (97)		
Finland[35]	1999 2011	0-19	2.7 8.3		
France[36]	2014	All ages	32[28-65] (89)		
Germany[37]	2008	All ages	2.5 [2.0-3.1] (87)		
	2009	All ages	1.0 [0.7-1.4] (34)		
	2010	All ages	1.3[1.0-1.7] (45)		
Italy[38]	2000-2003	0-17	5.9 (203)		
Italy[39]	2009-2010	≥18	12 (18)		

Spain[40]	2004-2005	0-4	313.6[230.5,416.8]	325.1[210.49-79.54]	301.45[189.01-456.05]
		5-9	74.4 [35.7, 136.8]	114.35[49.38-225.19]	31.06[3.76-112.14]
		10-14	112.5 [61.5, 188.7]	109.79[44.15-226.07]	115.4[46.41-237.62]
		15-19	124.5 [73.8, 196.7]	93.58[37.63-192.72]	157.64[78.72-281.88]
		20-24	124.5 [83.4, 178.8]	115.91[63.38-194.41]	133.83[74.92-220.64]
		25-29	84.1 [57.2, 119.4]	63.36[32.74-110.65]	106.07[63.88-165.6]
		30-34	72.9 [48.0, 106]	84.12[48.09-136.57]	61[30.45-109.11]
		35-39	94.2 [62.1, 137]	128.1[77.14-199.97]	57.79[24.95-113.83]
		40-44	153.4 [105.6, 215.3]	200.62[125.77-303.58]	104.25 [52.05-186.45]
		45-49	53.1 [24.3, 100.8]	12.49[0.316-69.57]	89.55[38.67-176.36]
		50-54	86.1 [50.1, 137.8]	56.46[18.33-131.71]	110.11[56.91-192.26]
		55-59	65.5 [38.2, 104.8]	66.81[28.85-131.6]	64.36[29.43-122.14]
		60-64	104.8 [66.5, 157.3]	72.89[31.47-143.56]	136.86[76.62-225.63]
		65-69	91.6 [47.3, 159.9]	15.09[0.382-84.03]	169.91[84.85-303.81]
		70-74	71.8 [28.9, 147.9]	108.93[35.38-254.03]	38.77[4.7-140]
		75-79	78 [25.3, 181.8]	0[0-135.73]	135.21[43.92-315.25]
		80-84	87.6 [23.9, 224.2]	61.0[51.55-339.67]	102.46[21.13-299.13]
85+	153.1 [56.2, 332.8]	0[0-331.78]	213.52[78.4-464.17]		
All ages		103.4 [92.6, 115] (336)	98.8[84.1,115.4] (159)	107.81[92.52-124.91] (177)	
Spain[41]	1998	All ages	1.35 [1.35-1.36] (528)	1.41 [1.40-1.41] (270)	1.30 [1.30-1.31] (258)
	1999		1.44 [1.44-1.44] (572)	1.54 [1.53-1.55] (299)	1.34[1.34-1.35] (273)
	2000		1.42 [1.42-1.43] (569)	1.60 [1.60-1.61] (314)	1.25 [1.25-1.26] (255)
	2001		1.54 [1.54-1.55] (628)	1.65 [1.64-1.66] (329)	1.44 [1.44-1.45] (299)
	2002		1.55 [1.55-1.56] (646)	1.67 [1.66-1.67] (341)	1.44[1.44-1.45] (305)
	2003		1.61 [1.60-1.61] (683)	1.79 [1.79-1.80] (375)	1.43[1.42-1.43] (308)
	2004		1.66 [1.66-1.66] (717)	1.79[1.79-1.80] (382)	1.53[1.52-1.53] (335)
	2005		1.71 [1.70-1.71] (755)	1.73 [1.72-1.73] (378)	1.69 [1.68-1.69] (377)
	2006		1.79 [1.78-1.79] (807)	1.93[1.92-1.93] (431)	1.65 [1.64-1.65] (376)
	2007		1.69 [1.68-1.69] (771)	1.82[1.81-1.82] (410)	1.56 [1.56-1.57] (361)
	2008		1.86 [1.86-1.86] (874)	1.95[1.95-1.96] (454)	1.77 [1.77-1.78] (420)
	2009		2.03 [2.03-2.04] (971)	2.22 [2.22-2.23] (527)	1.85 [1.84-1.85] (444)
	2010		2.43 [2.42-2.43] (1181)	2.63 [2.62-2.64] (631)	2.23 [2.22-2.23] (550)
	2011		2.38 [2.38-2.39] (1180)	2.61 [2.60-2.62] (638)	2.16 [2.16-2.17] (542)

Sweden[35]	1999 2011	0-19	4.3 15		
Switzerland[42]	1996-1998	4-85	a. (249)		
Turkiye[43]	2010-2011	All ages	1.95 [1.3-3.77] (114)		
UK[44]	2000/2001	0-14	4.1	3.4	4.1
		15-44	3.9		
		45+	3.5		
		Overall	3.8		
UK[45]	1994-1999	All ages	8.4		
UK[46]	2001	All ages	6.7 [5.7-7.7]		
	2002		6.6 [5.7-7.6]		
	2003		6.8 [5.9-7.9]		
	2004		8.5 [7.5-9.6]		
	2005		7.9 [7.0-9.0]		
UK[47]	1996-2005	10-79	34.38 [32.44-36.38] (382)		
UK[48]	1992	All ages	1.0		
	2012		7.0		
UK[49]	2012	< 16	35.9 [27.0,46.3] (105)		
		≥ 16	34.1[29.6,39.1] (321)		
		All ages	34.5[30.4,38.9] (426)		
European ADVANCE (Accelerated Development of Vaccine benefit-risk Collaboration in Europe) Project[50]					
<i>Note: Rates shown are for all ages unless otherwise noted.</i>					
Netherlands PHARMO Database Network	2017	Inpatient GP + inpatient	3.21 [2.85-3.60] 10.58 [7.80-14.03]		
Denmark Danish Registries (DCE-AU)	2010		10.06 [9.26-10.93]		
Spain BIFAP	2017	GP based	5.64 [5.17-6.14]		
		GP and inpatient	8.81 [7.94-9.75]		
Spain SIDIAP	2017	GP based	11.33 [10.47-12.24]		
		GP and inpatient	14.96 [13.09-17.06]		
Spain FISABIO	2017	In and outpatient	22.07 [20.84-23.37]		

Italy ARS database	2017	Inpatient only + Emergency room	7.90 [6.73-9.22]		
Italy PEDIANET database	2018	0-14 years GP based	3.40 [1.11-7.94]		
United Kingdom CPRD & HES	2017	All ages years GP based	19.71 [18.29-21.20]		
European ACCESS (The Vaccine covid-19 monitoring readiness project[51]) Case definition: https://zenodo.org/records/5236723					
<i>Note: All rates shown are for all ages.</i>					
Italy ^{PEDIANET} , Spain ^{BIFAP, SIDIAP} , UK ^{CPRD}	2017-2019	GP only	9.39[3.16-15.61]		
Netherlands ^{PHARMO}	2017-2019	INPATIENT only	6.82[0.00-13.71]		
Italy ^{ARS}	2017-2019	INPATIENT + EMR	7.44[5.54-9.33]		
Spain ^{FISABIO, BIFAP, SIDIAP} , Netherlands ^{PHARMO}	2017-2019	GP + INPATIENT + OUTPATIENT	14.17[7.46-20.87]		
Denmark ^{Danish registries} , France ^{SNDS}	for Danish registries: 2010–2013 and SNDS 2017-2020	INPATIENT + OUTPATIENT	11.30[10.04-12.56]		
Middle East					
Israel[52]	2008	≥ 18	7.35 (24)		
	2009		8.55 (30)		
	2010		7.83 (28)		
	2011		21.15 (77)		
	2012		36.26 (33)		
	2008-2012		16.2 (192)		
Multiple Global Regions					
Australia, France, Germany, Japan, Netherlands, Spain, UK, USA[53]	2017-2019	1-5		74 [26-209]	49[16-150]
		6-17		56[18-175]	50[16-154]
		18-34		29[14-63]	39[16-95]
		35-54		24[11-53]	34[13-91]
		55-64		25[11-53]	35[14-85]
		65-74		24[9-68]	29[11-76]

		75-84		18[7-49]	23[7-73]
		≥85		10[2-50]	12[4-36]

Table 2.2 Methodology for background rate studies in Table 2.1.

1 st Author and Locale	Code System	Database and Codes (boldface text if included in this Companion Guide Appendix 1; brief description provided including cause of anaphylaxis as appropriate. Full term provided for codes not included in Guide)	Additional details regarding case source, definition and validation
AMERICAS			
Nasreen Ontario, Canada[8]	ICD-10-CA	Canadian Institute for Health Information: Discharge Abstract Database and National Ambulatory Care Reporting System T78.2 (anaphylactic reaction), T80.5(serum), T88.6 (medicine)	Case Sources: hospital admissions and emergency room visits Not validated <i>Note: The codes listed were considered to be a broad definition of anaphylaxis. The authors also defined a narrow definition, using T78.2 and T80.5 only. Data in Table 2.1 are for the broad definition.</i>
Yocum, USA Minnesota[9]	Not identified	Rochester Epidemiology Project database (all care provided to Olmsted Country residents) Searched database for: anaphylaxis, food allergy, drug allergy, hypersensitivity. Not otherwise specified, adverse effect of immunotherapy, adverse effect of injectable diagnostic agent, subglottic or pharyngeal edema, bee sting allergy, unspecified allergic reaction.	Case Sources: all medical care visits Case Definition for anaphylaxis: had to have 1 symptom of generalized mediator release (flushing, pruritus/paresthesia, urticaria, angioedema) AND ≥1 oral/gastrointestinal or respiratory or cardiovascular symptom. Also included if isolated laryngeal edema or immediate reaction and syncopal event after injection of medication or radiocontrast agent. Validation: Physician medical record review
Lee, USA, Minnesota Olmsted County[10]	ICD-9	Rochester Epidemiology Project database (all care provided to Olmsted Country residents) For causes of anaphylaxis: 995.60-995.69 (food); 999.41(administration of blood and blood products); 999.42 (vaccination), 999.49 (other serum), 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction); V13.81(personal history of anaphylaxis Not specific for anaphylaxis V15.06 (allergy to insects and arachnids); E905.0-905.9 (poisoning and toxic reactions due to venomous: snakes, lizards, spiders, scorpions, hornets, wasps, bees, centipedes, millipedes, other venomous arthropods, marine animals and plants, other animals or plants, specified or unspecified); 989.5 (toxic effect of venom); 477.1 (allergic rhinitis due to food); 692.5 (contact dermatitis and other eczema due to food in contact with skin); 693.1(dermatitis due to food taken internally); 995.7 (other adverse food reactions, not elsewhere classified), V15.0x allergy to: ('x': 1=peanuts; 2=milk; 3=eggs; 4=seafood; 5=other foods); 988.x Toxic effect of things eaten as food: ('x': 0=fish or shellfish; 1=mushrooms; 2=berries and other plants; 8=other specified	Case Sources: all medical care visits Case Definition: NIAID/FAAN criteria (See Table 2.3) Validation: Medical review of all cases identified by codes listed as causes of anaphylaxis; and random sample of 20% of cases identified by codes not specific for anaphylaxis.

		noxious substance; 9=unspecified noxious substance; 995.2/995.21/995.27 (medication but unable to find specific ICD-9 terms for codes)	
Decker USA Minnesota[11]	ICD-9	Rochester Epidemiology Project database (all care provided to Rochester city residents, as opposed to all of Olmsted County) For causes of anaphylaxis: codes for anaphylactic shock due to food, sting or not otherwise classified; Not specific for anaphylaxis: codes for venom exposure or bee sting; toxic effect of venom; allergy to foodstuff; adverse effect of food; dermatitis caused by food taken internally; toxic effect of specific food.	Case Sources: medical visits by residents of Rochester city Case Definition and Validation: same as Yocum above
Bohlke USA Washington State[12]	ICD-9	Group Health Cooperative (HMO) administrative data For anaphylaxis (caused by): 995.6 (food); 999.4 (serum); 995.4 (anesthesia); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) Not specific or anaphylaxis: 989.5 (toxic effect of venom); 708.0 (allergic urticaria); 708.9 (urticaria, unspecified); 695.1 (erythema multiforme); 995.1 (angioneurotic edema); 995.3 (allergy, unspecified)	Case Sources: Pediatric hospital admissions and emergency or outpatient clinic visits Case definition: Probable case - ≥ 2 systems (Skin/mucosa, cardiac, respiratory, gastrointestinal), with onset ≤ 4 hrs after allergen exposure and treated with epinephrine, antihistamine, or steroids Possible case – missing 1 ‘probable’ criterion: [not treated] OR [time to onset unknown or > 4 hrs after allergen exposure] OR [only 1 system involved] Validation: medical record review Note: Calculated positive predictive value for probable or possible anaphylaxis: 995.0 = 55%; 995.6 – 10% (but rejected cases were mostly follow-up visits or specialty referrals for known allergy); 995.1 – 7.4%; 708.0 – 5.6%; 989.5 = 4.7%; 995.3 = 1.3%; 995.4, 999.4, 708.9 + 695.1 = 0%; <i>Incidence data in table 2.1 is based on specific anaphylaxis codes</i>
Michelson USA national[13]	Not provided	Nationwide Emergency Department Sample (NEDS) Specific codes not provided; focused on several different diseases separately to calculate incidence, including anaphylaxis	Case Sources: Pediatric emergency room visits classified as involving severe disease Not validated
Lin New York State, USA[14]	ICD-9	Statewide Planning and Research Cooperative System (SPARCS) 995.6 (food); 999.4 (serum); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction)	Case Sources: Acute care hospital admissions Not validated
Harduar-Morano, USA Florida[15]	ICD-9	Florida Agency for Health Care Administration database Two sets of codes used: Method 1: specific anaphylaxis code in one of 10 diagnostic fields: 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction);	Case Sources: Emergency room visits Case Definition: ICD-9-CM algorithm based on NIAID 2005 anaphylaxis CD. (see Table 2.3) Validation: Based on previous study (see Table 2.3 - Harduar-Morano 2010) which compared Method 2 to Method 1 and looked for consistency in clinical risk factors and demographics of cases.

		<p>Method 2: ICD-9 code algorithm based on other ICD-9 codes within 10 diagnosis fields and three Ecode fields. Had to meet one of a, b or c:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) codes for respiratory compromise or skin/mucosal involvement in conjunction with shock due to anesthesia; b) respiratory compromise or reduced blood pressure in conjunction with skin/mucosal involvement c) combination of (gastrointestinal symptoms, respiratory compromise, reduced blood pressure or skin mucosal involvement) in conjunction with a potential allergen (including venom, drugs, biological substance) <p>Excluded any duplicate cases found by both methods</p>	<p>No chart review done. Noted that Method 2 more likely to identify older individuals, those with hypertension or heart disease and those with venom-induced anaphylaxis. Of 2571 total cases 42% found with Method 1 and 58% with Method 2. Only 26 cases were identified by both methods. The study publication is open access and includes supplemental tables that provide more detail on the algorithm.</p>
Pourang, USA S. California [16]	ICD-9	<p>Kaiser Permanente; For causes of anaphylaxis: 995.60-.69 (foods); 995.4 (anesthesia); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) Not specific for anaphylaxis 989.5 (venom toxicity), 995.1 (angioneurotic edema), Poisoning and toxic reaction due to: E905.3(hornet/wasp/bee sting), E905.5 (other venomous arthropods), E905.8/.9(other specified or unspecified animals and plants)</p>	<p>Case Sources: All Kaiser Permaenente health care resources Validation: chart review to validate a subset of cases with ICD-9 code 995.3 and only 15 of 200 were confirmed as anaphylaxis. For this reason excluded cases with 995.3 code. Also excluded codes 995.2 based on review of 10 cases. Note: rates shown in Table 2.1 are substantially higher than found in other studies. Not clear why but noted that for the 995.0 and 995.6 coded cases, epinephrine auto-injectors were prescribed for 49.3% and 58.6% respectively. For all remaining codes auto-injectors were prescribed in ≤16.2%.</p>
Motosue USA, national [17]	ICD-9	<p>Optum Labs Insurance database; 2 methods to find anaphylaxis cases: Method 1: 995.60-.69 (foods); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction); Method 2: see Harduar-Moreno above</p>	<p>Case Sources: emergency department visits Not validated but did use Harduar-Moreno’s validated algorithm (see table 2.3) to find cases in addition to specific anaphylaxis codes</p>
Hoyos-Bachiloglu, Chile [18]	ICD-10	<p>Ministry of Health national hospital discharge database; T78.0 (food); T88.6 (medicine); T78.2 (unspecified cause)</p>	<p>Case Sources: hospital admissions Not validated</p>
ASIA			
Ho China [19]	ICD-9	<p>For causes of anaphylaxis: 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) Not specific for anaphylaxis 995.1 (angioneurotic edema)</p>	<p>Case Sources: pediatric hospital admissions Case definition: NIAID/FAAN criteria (see Table 2.3) Validation: medical chart review for 100 of 104 cases. Note: 40 cases confirmed to be anaphylaxis (included 25 coded as angioneurotic edema only).</p>
Wang China	ICD-9	<p>Hong Kong Clinical Data Analysis and Reporting System (all hospitals) 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction)</p>	<p>Case Sources: pediatric hospital admissions and emergency visits Not validated</p>

Hong Kong[20]			
Yang South Korea[21]	ICD-10	Korean National health Insurance claims database T78.0 (food); T80.5 (serum) T88.6 (medicine); T78.2 (unspecified cause)	Case Sources: visits to any medical institution in Korea Not validated
Liew Singapore[22]	Not provided	Singapore KK Women’s and Children’s Hospital databases Anaphylaxis identified via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discharge codes of hospital admissions • discharge codes from Department of Children’s Emergency • referrals made to the hospital Allergy service outpatient clinics 	Case Sources: admissions, ED visits, referrals to allergy OPD clinics Case definition: NIAID/FAAN Validation: medical chart review by allergists to assess if cases met case definition criteria and had confirmed allergen trigger 98 children with 108 anaphylaxis events due to unique allergens. Excluded 10 cases of recurrent events triggered by same allergen.
AUSTRALIA/OCEANIA			
Mullins 2003 Australia[23]	ICD-9	National Hospital Morbidity Database 995.4 (anesthesia); 995.6 (food); 999.4 (serum); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction)	Case Sources: patients referred for anaphylaxis to community-based medical specialists in the Australian Capital Territory Case definition: ≥2 of: urticaria/angioedema; bronchospasm; gastrointestinal symptoms; hypotension. Validation: based on referral clinic medical diagnosis and clinical data from hospital admission
Poulos Australia[24]	ICD-9 ICD-10	National hospital morbidity database and National Mortality Database 995.6 (food); 999.4 (serum); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) T78.0 (food); T80.5 (serum) T88.6 (medicine); T78.2 (unspecified cause)	Case Sources: hospital admissions, deaths diagnosis Not validated <i>Note: Included cases of all ages (0->65yrs) but only provided specific incidence data for 0-4 year olds.</i>
Mullins 2007 Australia[25]	ICD-9 ICD-10	National hospital morbidity database 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause) Excluded T88.6 (medicines) because no comparable code in ICD-9; also excluded sting anaphylaxis because not possible to distinguish anaphylaxis from other ‘toxic’ reactions.	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Case definition: ASCIA (see table 2.3) Not validated <i>Note: study focus was on children aged 0-5 years referred to one community based practice of immunology-allergy specialists in the Australian Capital Territory for allergy-related disorders including total anaphylaxis and food anaphylaxis These cases were validated by the specialists based on the ASCIA case definition diagnosed with food-induced anaphylaxis. The authors also looked at hospital admissions for anaphylaxis across all ages, based on ICD codes, without validation. These are the data presented in Table 2.1</i>
Mullins 2009 Australia[26]	ICD-10	National Hospital Morbidity Database Principal Diagnosis data T78.0 (food); T88.6 (medication); T80.5 (serum); T78.2 (unspecified cause) Excluded sting anaphylaxis because not possible to distinguish anaphylaxis from other ‘toxic’ reactions.	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Not validated

Mullins 2015 Australia[27]	ICD-10	National hospital morbidity database T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause) – had to be principle diagnosis	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Not validated Note: <i>calculated rates for all anaphylaxis (shown in table 5.1) as well as incidence for specific causes: food, medication, serum and unclassified anaphylaxis separately (data not shown in table 5.1)</i>
Mullins 2016 Australia[28]	ICD-9 ICD-10	National hospital morbidity database 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction); 999.4 (serum) T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T80.5 (serum); T88.6 (medicine)	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Not validated Note: <i>main focus of study was to look at changing anaphylaxis related mortality by cause of anaphylaxis. The data in Table 2.1, hospital admissions/100,000 population for anaphylaxis in 1997 and 2013 were done to provide an all case comparator for changes in mortality over time. The mortality data are not shown.</i>
Andrew Australia Victoria State[29]	Not provided	Ambulance Victoria data warehouse	Case Source: EMS services Case definition: sudden onset of ≥ 2 of: respiratory distress, gastrointestinal symptoms, skin/mucosal symptoms OR hypotension AND treated with epinephrine on emergency basis by EMS or self-treatment with autoinjector Validation: by review of demographic and clinical data.
Pillsbury Australia New South Wales State[30]	ICD-10-AM SNOMEDCT	New South Wales databases: APDC, EDDC, Mortality datasets For hospitalized cases: Narrow case definition: T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T80.5 (serum); T88.6 (medicine) Broad case definition: all of above plus other codes under T78 including angioedema, histamine release, venom hypersensitivity and passive cutaneous anaphylaxis. For emergency room cases: 30 different codes identified for searching and defined in supplemental material to publication; basically broad search for all cause anaphylactic shock, anaphylaxis or anaphylactoid reaction	Case Source: hospital admissions, emergency department visits Not Validated Case definition: code based; ICD-10 codes shown were part of a narrow definition. For a broad definition used same codes plus T78 which includes much more than anaphylaxis (angioedema, histamine release, venom hypersensitivity, passive cutaneous anaphylaxis). Note: <i>Table 2.1 only presents incidence using narrow case definition.</i>
EUROPE			
Sorenson Denmark[31]	Not provided	Single hospital medical records and Danish National Registry of Deaths All cases with diagnosis of “collapsus anaphylacticus”	Case Source: hospital admissions or deaths Case definition: Cardiovascular collapse, hypotension or unconsciousness Validation: review of hospital records
Jeppesen Denmark[32]	ICD-10	Danish National Patient Registry T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T80.5 (serum); T88.6 (medicine); T63.4 (toxic effect of venom of other arthropods)	Case Source: Hospital admissions Not validated

Norreedam Denmark[33]	ICD-10	Danish National Patient Registry T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T80.5 (serum); T88.6 (medicine); T63.4 (toxic effect of venom of other arthropods)	Case Source: 1 st time hospital admissions, Emergency room contacts and outpatient visits Not validated Note: <i>calculated separate rates for Danish born (included in Table 2.1) as well as western and non-western immigrants (neither included in Table 2.1).</i>
Kivisto Finland and Sweden[35]	ICD-10	Finnish National Hospital Discharge Register; Swedish National Patient Register T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause);	Case Source: Hospital admissions Case definition: severe, potentially fatal, systemic allergic reaction that occurs suddenly after contact with or ingestion of allergy-causing substances Not validated Note: <i>Incidence denominators based on entire country child populations and so no 95% confidence intervals or p values calculated</i>
Tanno France[36]	ICD-10	Single hospital For causes of anaphylaxis: T78.0(food), T78.2(unspecified cause), T80.5 (serum) Not specific for anaphylaxis T78.1(other adverse food reactions, not elsewhere classified), T78.3(angioneurotic edema), T78.4 (allergy, unspecified), T78.8 (other adverse effects, not elsewhere classified); T78.9 (adverse effect, unspecified)	Case Source: hospital admissions Case definition: ≥2 systems (skin, respiratory, gastrointestinal, cardiac) Validation: manual chart review by two trained allergists. Note: <i>Of 673 files with ICD-10 codes related to anaphylaxis, 309 files clinically validated as anaphylaxis case (89 = 20%) or allergic/hypersensitivity comorbidities (220 = 71%).</i>
Beyer Germany[37]	Not applicable	Two year prospective study in 18 emergency departments in Berlin. Standardized form provided for use for any patients seen experiencing a severe allergic reaction.	Case Source: emergency room visits Case definition: EMS services activated for patients with severe respiratory (dyspnea, stridor or apnea) and/or severe cardiovascular (hypotension, tachycardia, loss of consciousness, or cardiac arrest) symptoms. Excluded reactions with skin only. Validation: For every patient seen with severe allergic reaction ER physicians asked to complete a standardized questionnaire for detailed information on symptoms of severe allergic reactions, proposed elicitors and emergency treatment given.
Calvani Italy[38]	ICD-9	Lazio Region Public Health Agency Hospital and Emergency Health Information Systems 995.4 (anesthesia); 995.6 (food); 999.4 (serum); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction)	Case Sources: hospital admission (could be overnight or in a daytime hospital for observation) Not validated Note: <i>rates in table 2.1 are for all four codes shown. They also calculated age-specific rates for each code (not shown in table)</i>

Lauritano Italy[39]	ICD-9	Single hospital inpatient and emergency department records 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) 995.1 (angioedema); 995.3 (allergy/allergic reaction); 493.9 (allergic asthma); 708.0 (allergic urticaria)	Case Sources: Emergency room visits for first episode of anaphylaxis. Case definition: 4 acute allergy patient groups: 1: only skin; 2: only respiratory; 3: only gastrointestinal; 4. anaphylaxis: severe, generalised or systemic hypersensitivity reaction rapidly developing life-threatening airway and/or breathing and/or circulation problems. Validation: medical record review
Ruiz Oropesa Denmark[34]	ICD-10	Single pediatric hospital including emergency room Codes for allergy, anaphylaxis or treatment with adrenaline, antihistamines or glucocorticoids	Case Sources: hospital admission, emergency room visit Case definition: WAO/EAACI criteria (see table 2.3) Validation: manual review of clinical records
Tejedor-Alonso 2012 Spain[40]	Text strings in electronic databases	Computerized Clinical records for city of Alcorcon. Terms included: allergy, anaphylaxis, urticaria, hypersensitivity, erythema, bite, edema, drug, reaction, food, honeybee, wasp and adverse. Specific code used for anaphylaxis in the Allergy Outpatient Clinic.	Case Sources: hospital admissions, emergency room visits, specialty clinic visits Case definition: NIAID/FAAN (see table 2.3) Validation: medical record review by emergency physicians and allergists/immunologists <i>Note: Authors present the % of cases by clinical setting. Hospital admissions accounted for only 5.95% of cases; 56% were seen in emergency department and 71.4% in primary care without admission.</i>
Tejedor-Alonso 2015 Spain[41]	ICD-9	Spanish Minimum Basic Data Set (MBDS) Two approaches to finding cases: 1. ICD-9 codes associated with anaphylaxis/causes of anaphylaxis 2. Algorithm with codes for causes of anaphylaxis as well as organ system symptoms or signs that met the case definition.	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Case definition: NIAID/FAAN Not validated but approach 2 used Harduar-Moreno’s validated algorithm (see table 2.3) to find cases in addition to specific anaphylaxis codes. <i>Note: The rates in Table 5.1 are for all cause anaphylaxis. The paper also provides separate rates by year for: food-, drug- and unknown cause- anaphylaxis.</i>
Helbling Switzerland[42]	ICD-10	Medical records from two allergy clinics in Bern plus requests to all local MDs and Hospitals with emergency units for any anaphylaxis cases that may not have been referred to the allergy clinics. ICD-10 codes used for searching fatal cases of anaphylaxis, but incident cases were identified as noted above, without specific codes.	Case Sources: allergy clinic assessment of referred patients plus survey of community physicians and hospital emergency rooms for any anaphylaxis cases not referred to allergy clinic Case definition: severe systemic anaphylaxis with circulatory symptoms consistent with generalized mast cell-mediated reaction (hypotension, unconsciousness or shock). Validation: case medical review and anaphylaxis final diagnosis based on allergy work up including allergy testing

			Note: Incidence data in table 2.1 are for severe anaphylaxis with circulatory compromise
Cetinkaya Türkiye[43]	ICD-10	Istanbul Health Directorate Network regional database: data from all 45 hospitals in Istanbul Anaphylaxis T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T80.5 (serum); T88.6 (medicine); ≥2 Symptoms & Signs indicative of anaphylaxis Skin/mucosa: L50.0 (allergic urticaria), L50.9 (urticaria-unspecified); L27.0 (generalized skin eruption due to drugs and medicaments); R60.1 (generalized edema) Cardiovascular: I95.2 (hypotension due to drugs; I95.0 (idiopathic hypotension; R57 (shock, not elsewhere classified) Respiratory: R06.2 (wheezing), R09.0 (asphyxia); R06.0 (dyspnea); R09.2 (respiratory arrest) Gastrointestinal: R11 (nausea and vomiting) Nervous system: R55 (syncope and collapse)	Case Sources: Hospital admissions Not validated Note: identified 79 cases with anaphylaxis codes and 35 with combination of symptoms and signs
Gupta UK[44]	ICD-9 ICD-10	Hospital Episodes Statistics (HES) 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) T78.2 (unspecified cause);	Case Sources: hospital admissions Not validated
Peng UK[45]	Oxford Medical Information Systems Code	GPRD database; Codes for anaphylaxis (trigger or other related term): 9779AK (anaphylactic shock due to medication); 9779AR (anaphylactic reaction due to medicine or drug); 9894HA (bite(s), animal); 9894HB (bee sting); 9894HN (reaction to bite); 9899AN (non-medicinal agent); 9994 (anaphylactic shock or reaction); 9994CC (vaccination); 9994MN (immunization); 9994RM (serum). OR diagnosis of anaphylaxis noted in a comment	Case Sources: Hospital admissions, emergency rooms, GP visits Case definition: not specified Validation: for random sample of 70 patients with diagnosis based on code(s) and 50 with diagnosis based on comment. asked attending GP for diagnostic info (specialist referral letters or notes from hospital or emergency rooms) – Note: of 120 cases reviewed 87 (72.5%) confirmed as anaphylaxis. Applied this to 897 cases identified and included 675 cases for incidence calculation.
Sheikh UK[46]	READ	QRESEARCH database (data from 525 UK general practices) Specific codes for anaphylaxis not specified	Case Source: GP practice recorded diagnosis of anaphylaxis Not validated
Gonzalez-Perez UK[47]	ICD-9	THIN database (>2.3 million patients registered with >300 GP practices) For causes of anaphylaxis: 995.4 (anesthesia); 995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction) Non-specific for anaphylaxis:	Case Sources: GP practices. Divided population into 3 subgroups: Validation: GPs asked to complete structured questionnaire with patient clinical information looking for symptoms and therapy consistent with anaphylaxis. Only confirmed cases included. Note: confirmation rate 85.3% or specific codes versus 70.2% for nonspecific codes

		<p>693.1 (dermatitis due to food); 695.1 (erythema multiforme); 708.0 (allergic urticaria); 708.9 (urticaria unspecified); 989.5 (toxic effect of venom); 995.1 (angioneurotic edema); 995.3 (allergy unspecified)</p> <p>Identified 3 population subgroups based on ICD-9 codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asthma: 493.0 (extrinsic asthma); 493.1 (intrinsic asthma); 493.9 (asthma unspecified) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Severe asthma: ≥1 of: hospitalized for asthma; OR within one year, [≥3 prescriptions for oral steroids OR ≥12 prescriptions for inhaled beta 2-agonists OR ≥3 classes of asthma medications] Non-severe asthma: didn't meet definition for severe No asthma cohort: random sample of 200,000 without a diagnosis of asthma matched to asthma cohort by age, sex 	
Turner UK[48]	<p>ICD-9¹⁹⁹²⁻⁹⁷ ICD-10¹⁹⁹⁸⁻²⁰¹²</p>	<p>England and Wales hospital admission and fatalities databases</p> <p>995.6 (food); 995.0 (other anaphylactic reaction)</p> <p>T78.0 (food); T78.2 (unspecified cause); T88.6 (medicine)</p> <p>X23 (secondary code used in conjunction with T78 to identify insect sting related anaphylaxis)</p>	<p>Case Sources: hospital admissions</p> <p>Not validated</p> <p>Note: Table 2.1 provides incidence for 1992 and 2012 as these were the only specific numbers provided in the text. See article for figures showing trends by year and sex, as well as by trigger, throughout the study period. Also provide epi of fatal anaphylaxis.</p>
Buka UK[49]	Not stated	<p>Emergency room database from 3 acute care hospitals in or near Birmingham.</p> <p>Search terms: Anaphylaxis, anaphylactic shock, angioedema, allergic reaction, Skin – allergic reaction, Bite-Insect Venom, Bite – Insect Non Venom, Skin rash other.</p>	<p>Case Sources: emergency room visits</p> <p>Case definition: World Allergy Organization (WAO) criteria (see table 2.3).</p> <p>Validation: Manual review of emergency department records and ambulance crew records to confirm cases meeting WAO criteria</p> <p>Total of 426 cases in 395 individuals included for incidence calculation. Thus, some individuals were counted twice.</p> <p>Note: Authors calculated separate incidence rates for all versus severe anaphylaxis (Brown scale - see table 2.3) and for 'South Asians' (Origin India, Pakistan, Bangladesh) vs White ethnicity.</p> <p>Table 2.1 only shows incidence for total population and age group.</p>
Willame 2021&2023 Europe[50, 51]	Multiple coding systems	<p>Different databases for each country – specified in table 2.1</p> <p>Codes unique to each database and system but are published at this link: https://zenodo.org/records/5236723</p>	<p>Case Sources: varied by country but could include hospital admissions, emergency room visits, physician offices. Specified in table 2.1.</p> <p>Not validated</p>
MIDDLE EAST			
Hananashvili Israel[52]	Not stated	Single university medical center	<p>Case Sources: hospital admissions, emergency department visits</p> <p>Case definition: NIAID / FAAN (see Table 2.3)</p>

		Searched for diagnosis of: anaphylactic shock or reaction or allergic reaction from any cause.	Validation: Medical record review by 2 independent reviewers
MULTIPLE CONTINENTS			
Li Multiple countries[53]	Varied ICD-10 ICD-9 READ ICPC-1 KCD7	8 countries (France, Germany, Netherlands, Spain, United Kingdom, Australia, Japan, USA) - 13 unique databases (8 electronic health records; administrative claims – fully described in the publication. T78.2, T80.52, T80.59, T80.5, T80.52XA, T78.2XXA, T80.59XD, T78.2XXD, T80.52XD, T80.59XA 999.4, 99.42, 995, 999.49 SP34.00, SN50.00, SN50.11 A12.01 T78.2, T80.5	Case Sources: hospital admissions, emergency room visits Case definition: Used predefined phenotyping algorithm based on diagnostic codes from claims data and problem lists from electronic health records. Not validated

Table 2.3. Anaphylaxis case definitions cited in methodology presented in Table 2.3 above

Source	Definition or Criteria
National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Disease (NAIAD) and Food Allergy and Anaphylaxis Network (FAAN)[54]	Must fulfill ≥1 of 3 criteria: (note: time period for all yellow highlighted phrases is minutes to several hours) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acute onset of an illness with involvement of the skin, mucosal tissue or both and at least one of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Respiratory compromise (e.g., dyspnoea, bronchospasm, stridor, hypoxia) b. Cardiovascular compromise (e.g., hypotension, collapse) 2. ≥2 of a, b, c or d below that occur rapidly after exposure to a likely allergen for that patient <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Involvement of the skin or mucosal tissue (e.g., generalised hives, itch, flushing, swelling) b. Respiratory compromise (e.g., dyspnoea, bronchospasm, stridor, hypoxia) c. Cardiovascular compromise (e.g., hypotension, collapse) d. Persistent gastrointestinal symptoms (e.g. abdominal pain and vomiting) 3. Hypotension after exposure to known allergen for that patient: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Children - defined as systolic blood pressure of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. 1 month to 1 year old: systolic blood pressure <70 mmHg ii. 1 to ≤10 years old: <70mmHg + [2x age] iii. 11 to < 18 years old: <90 mmHg
World Allergy Organization (WAO)[55] and European Academy	Anaphylaxis highly likely when any of the following 3 criteria met: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sudden skin and/or mucosal tissue symptoms together with respiratory compromise and/or severe hypotension (systolic <90 mmHg for adults; age-specific for children) and/or end-organ dysfunction.

<p>of Allergy and Clinical Immunology (EAACI)[56]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Symptoms from ≥ 2 organ systems (skin and/or mucosal; respiratory; cardiovascular; gastrointestinal, suddenly after exposure to a likely allergen. 3. Severe hypotension after exposure to a known allergen for that patient <p>Validation: cases referred to Allergy Center where standardized interview conducted re anaphylaxis.</p>
<p>Australian Society of Clinical Immunology and Allergy (ASCIA)[57]</p>	<p>A rapidly evolving multisystem allergic reaction involving the presence of one or more symptoms or signs of hypotension or respiratory distress, and involvement of other organs such as the skin or gastrointestinal tract.</p>
<p>ICD-9 Algorithm[58]</p>	<p>Based on NIAID/FAAN criteria ICD-9-CM codes for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin-mucosal tissue involvement was found in conjunction with shock due to anesthesia (995.4) • Respiratory compromise was found in conjunction with shock due to anesthesia (995.4) or angioneurotic edema (995.1) • Reduced blood pressure (BP) was found in conjunction with skin-mucosal involvement, angioneurotic edema (995.1), the toxic effect of venom (989.5), or an Ecode indicating the cause of poisoning was a venomous animal/plant (E905, E905.3, E905.5, E905.8, E905.9) • Reduced BP and gastrointestinal symptoms were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), or an unspecified allergic reaction (995.3) • Reduced BP and skin-mucosal tissue involvement were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), or an unspecified allergic reaction (995.3) • Respiratory compromise and reduced BP were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), or an unspecified allergic reaction (995.3) • Respiratory compromise and gastrointestinal symptoms were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), an unspecified allergic reaction (995.3), skin-mucosal involvement, the toxic effect of venom (989.5), or an Ecode indicating the cause of poisoning was a venomous animal/plant (E905, E905.3, E905.5, E905.8, E905.9) • Respiratory compromise and skin-mucosal tissue involvement were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), an unspecified allergic reaction (995.3), the toxic effect of venom (989.5), or an Ecode indicating the cause of poisoning was a venomous animal/plant (E905, E905.3, E905.5, E905.8, E905.9) • Gastrointestinal symptoms and skin-mucosal tissue involvement were found in conjunction with an unspecified adverse effect due to the correct administration of a drug, medicinal, and biologic substance (995.2), an unspecified

	<p>allergic reaction (995.3), the toxic effect of venom (989.5), or an Ecode indicating the cause of poisoning was a venomous animal/plant (E905, E905.3, E905.5, E905.8, E905.9)</p> <p>Codes to define symptom categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respiratory compromise: acute respiratory failure (518.81), acute respiratory distress (518.82), dyspnea/respiratory distress (786, 786.00–786.09), stridor (786.1), extrinsic asthma (493.0) or unspecified asthma (493.9). • Reduced BP: hypotension (458, 458.0, 458.2, 458.8, 458.9), or syncope/collapse (780.2). • Gastrointestinal symptoms: allergic gastroenteritis/colitis (558.3), nausea/vomiting (787.0), nausea with vomiting (787.01), vomiting alone (787.03), or abdominal pain (789.0). • Skin-mucosal involvement: Conjunctival edema (372.73), Edema of eyelid (374.82), Edema of larynx (478.6), Edema of pharynx or nasopharynx (478.25), Flushing (782.62), Urticaria (708), Allergic urticaria (708.0), Idiopathic urticaria (708.1), Urticaria due to cold and heat (708.2), Dermatographic urticaria (708.3), Vibratory urticaria (708.4), Cholinergic urticaria (708.5), Other specified urticaria (708.8), Urticaria, unspecified (708.9), Pruritus and related conditions (698), Pruritus of genital organs (698.1), Other specified pruritic conditions (698.8), Unspecified pruritic disorder (698.9)
<p>Severity grading for generalized hypersensitivity reactions[59]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mild (skin and subcutaneous tissues only): Generalized erythema, urticaria, periorbital edema or angioedema 2. Moderate (features suggesting respiratory, cardiovascular or gastrointestinal involvement): dyspnea, stridor, wheeze, nausea, vomiting, dizziness (presyncope), diaphoresis, chest or throat tightness or abdominal pain. 3. Severe (hypoxia, hypotension or neurologic compromise): cyanosis or SpO₂ ≤92% at any stage, hypotension – systolic blood pressure <90mm Hg in adults, confusion, collapse, loss of consciousness or incontinence.

APPENDIX 3

Anaphylaxis Risk Factors

Anaphylaxis Risk Factors

Relative to the 2 previous Companion Guides for Anaphylaxis, this guide has a different approach to the risk factor summary table. Rather than having a single table, there are now three. Table 3.1 summarizes the known triggers for an anaphylactic reaction. It is beyond the scope of this guide to list all triggers but the main categories, and the most common specific triggers in each category are provided. Table 3.2 provides an overview of the risk factors that increase the incidence of an anaphylactic reaction in general. Finally, Table 3.3 provides a summary of what is known about risk factors for severe, including fatal, anaphylactic reactions.

With respect to the vaccine-anaphylaxis association, Table 3.1 includes a general summary regarding vaccine as a trigger. Evidence for specific vaccine – anaphylaxis associations is presented, by vaccine, in the following tables: Measles containing vaccines in Table 3.4; COVID-19 vaccines in Table 3.5; Influenza vaccines in Table 3.6; HPV vaccines in Table 3.7; Pneumococcal vaccines in Table 3.8; Other vaccines in Table 3.9.

TABLE 3.1 ANAPHYLAXIS TRIGGERS

In a summary of 730 cases of anaphylaxis seen at the Cleveland clinic, 29.9% were triggered by food, 24.6% by hymenoptera stings, 13.3% by medication, 4% were in a perioperative context, 3% by immunotherapy, 3% by radiocontrast media, 3% by exercise, 2% by latex, 1% in the context of mastocytosis and 13.7% were considered idiopathic with no discernible trigger.[60] More detail on the various triggers is provided in the table below.

Age	No evidence found
Sex	Semen/seminal fluid hypersensitivity [82]
Genetic	No evidence found
Pregnancy	No evidence found
Pre-/Peri-/Post-Natal Condition	No evidence found
Social/Culture	No evidence found
Occupation	No evidence found
Season	No evidence found
Geo-Location	No evidence found
Environment	Cold-induced anaphylaxis is triggered by cooling, via whole-body water immersion primarily, and less frequently by cold air exposure or cold drinks, in individuals with cold-induced urticaria[78, 79]. Latex rubber products (e.g. gloves, balloons) can induce anaphylaxis highly sensitive individuals[81] Airborne anaphylaxis can involve several different triggers including aerosolized food (e.g. peanuts, dill, egg, ginseng, mushroom, lentils), animal allergens (e.g. guinea pig, rabbit), latex, and drugs (e.g. volatile anesthetics).[80] For drugs,

	the trigger could be food-based such as soy lecithin used in ipratropium bromide inhalers or milk protein traces in drugs using lactose as an excipient .
Diet	<p>Most common food triggers are peanuts, tree nuts, shellfish, egg and milk. While the relative proportions may vary by population and clinical context, the Cleveland clinic study found prevalence among all food allergies was 23.9%, 21.6%, 16.1%, 10.1% and 10.1% respectively.[60, 61]</p> <p>Alpha-gal hypersensitivity [62, 63]</p> <p>Alpha-gal refers to galactose alpha 1,2-galactose which is present in non-primate meats (e.g., beef, pork, lamb venison, rabbit) and other animal derived products including gelatin, heparin, glycerin, as well as milk and milk products.</p> <p>Ticks contain Alpha-gal in their saliva and a bite can lead to sensitization. Specific ticks vary by region: lone star tick in US, <i>Ixodes holocyclus</i> in Australias, <i>Ixodes ricinus</i> in Europe.</p> <p>Two different presentations depending on the specific source of exposure to Alpha-gal[64]</p> <p>Delayed onset (by 2-6 hours)[65], after meat ingestion; relevant to anaphylaxis following immunization</p> <p>Immediate onset after receiving cetuximab (monoclonal antibody used to treat metastatic colorectal cancer). Alpha-gal is present within the antigen binding portion of the cetuximab heavy chain.</p> <p>Hidden causes in foods[66] Nanagas et al reviewed food-induced anaphylaxis where the cause is not apparent (e.g. beer with wheat components). It is beyond the scope of the guide to list all, but it is an excellent resource.</p>
Behavior	Exercise-induced anaphylaxis may be non-allergen dependent (i.e., no trigger but exercise) but this is very rare. Most cases include exposure to a food allergen prior to exercise, and include a wide variety of foods (wheat, shellfish, eggs, various fruit and vegetables and others).[76] Drug-dependent exercise induced anaphylaxis has also been reported with NSAIDS the most commonly associated drug.[77]
Comorbidity	No evidence found
Iatrogenic/Injury/Trauma	No evidence found
Infection	Hydatid cysts caused by <i>Echinococcus sp</i> : the first indication of the presence of a hydatid cyst can be anaphylaxis following blunt trauma which leads to cyst ruptura. This is rare, but a relevant consideration in endemic areas.[83]
Medication	<p>The most commonly cited drugs triggering anaphylaxis from multiple different areas of the world, are antibiotics and analgesics. It is beyond the scope of this guide to list all possible causes, but other notable ones are radio contrast media (iodinated and gadolinium containing), neuromuscular blockers, monoclonal antibodies, chemotherapeutic agents, especially those that bind to T cells, macrophages or monocytes, chondroitin sulfate, TNF-alpha inhibitors [67].</p> <p>Among antibiotics, beta-lactams, cephalosporins, vancomycin, quinolones and sulfonamides are most commonly implicated[68]</p> <p>Anesthetics including suxamethonium, pancuronium, atracurium[68]</p> <p>polyethylene glycol (PEG)[69, 70]</p>

	<p>Rossi et al reviewed anaphylaxis in adults and noted different pathways for drug-induced anaphylaxis[65]</p> <p>IgE mediated: antibiotics especially beta-lactams; nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory agents (NSAIDS); neuromuscular blockers;</p> <p>Cytokine storm: monoclonal antibodies, chemotherapeutic agents that bind to T cells, macrophages or monocytes</p> <p>Complement activation: chondroitin sulfate, radiologic procedure contrast media</p> <p>Direct mast-cell activation: vancomycin</p> <p>Anaphylaxis has been reported after compounds used in Alternative Medicines including ginseng, Ginkgo Biloba, Andrographis paniculata, Echinacea and Asteraceae (dandelion, ragweed, sunflower) but evidence is lacking for a causal association.[71]</p>
<p>Toxin/Toxic Exposures</p>	<p>Hymenoptera stings are a prevalent cause of anaphylaxis globally in both children and adults but the specific type of sting may vary geographically. In North America, Europe and Asia, honeybees, wasps and hornets are implicated. Fire ants are cited in Latin America and Asia as well.[75]</p>
<p>VACCINE</p>	<p>While vaccine, as a biologic material, could be included in drugs, it is in a separate row given its relevance to vaccine safety. Vaccines vary greatly in terms of content (antigen with or without adjuvant, preservative, stabilizers such as sucrose, lactose, glycine, gelatin or human serum albumin, and trace residuals of substances such as antibiotics, egg or yeast proteins). It is now understood that anaphylactic reactions to vaccines containing gelatin (not currently, but in the past included some MMR, MMRV, VZV, Herpes Zoster and Yellow Fever vaccine products) was most likely related to Alpha-gal hypersensitivity (see Food triggers above).</p> <p>Institute of Medicine 2011[72] concluded that evidence convincingly supports an association between MMR, VZV, influenza, Hepatitis B, meningococcal and tetanus toxoid vaccines and anaphylaxis; they also concluded that evidence favors acceptance of a causal relationship between HPV vaccine and anaphylaxis. In all instances the evidence that contributed to the conclusion was mechanistic consisting of multiple case reports.</p> <p>Updated review[73] of evidence published since 2011 IOM report agreed with and did not add any additional vaccine – anaphylaxis associations. They noted the attributable risk was 1 in 100,000 to 1 in 1,000,000 doses.</p> <p>The US Vaccine Safety Datalink studied the rate of anaphylaxis, confirmed using the Brighton case definition, following child and adult vaccination.[74] A total of 33 confirmed (Brighton level 1 or 2) cases of anaphylaxis occurred after 25,173,965 doses for a rate of 1.31 (95% Confidence Interval, 0.90-1.84) per million vaccine doses. There was a total of 17,606,500 vaccination visits for a rate of 1.87 (95% CI 1.29-2.63) per million visits. 85% of cases had a history of atopy. The implicated vaccines involved all those considered as causal by IOM (see first bullet above) and in addition: pneumococcal polysaccharide 23 valent (1 given alone, 1 with influenza vaccine), Herpes Zoster vaccine (1 given alone, 1 with allergy shot), rabies (1 given alone), Hepatitis A (1 given alone, 3 given with concomitant vaccines) Time to onset was:</p> <p><30 minutes - 8 (24.2%)</p>

	<p>30-<120 minutes – 8 (24.2%) 2 - <4 hours – 10 (30.3%) 4 – 8 hours – 2 (6.1%) Next day – 1 (3%) Not documented – 4 (12.1%)</p>
Other	<p>Idiopathic anaphylaxis occurs in the absence of an identifiable trigger. Recurrent reaction with no consistent trigger. Approximately two-thirds of individuals have 5 or less episodes per year; remainder have >5 episodes / year.[84, 85] Most common in females with known atopy history.[68, 84] Hereditary alpha-tryptasemia[86] and Mastocytosis[87] should be considered in cases of idiopathic anaphylaxis, especially in individuals with recurrent episodes or insect- or venom-induced anaphylaxis presenting with hypotensive syncope.</p>

TABLE 3.2. RISK FACTORS FOR ALL-CAUSE ANAPHYLAXIS

Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anaphylaxis occurs at all ages but the triggers may differ: in children food is the predominant trigger whereas in adults medication and insect venom are more prevalent[84]
Sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Males – more common in those aged <15 years[68] Females – more common in those aged >15 years[68]
Genetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atopy[68, 84]– multigenic including genes for cytokines and IgE receptor Hereditary Alpha-tryptasemia – an autosomal dominant genetic trait found in 5% of Caucasians[86, 88]. Affected individuals have elevated basal serum tryptase levels which are directly related to the number of extra copies (1-4) of the TPSAB1 gene.
Pregnancy	No evidence found
Pre-/Peri-/Post-Natal Condition	No evidence found
Social / Culture	No evidence found
Occupation	No evidence found
Season	No evidence found
Geo-location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More common in High Income Countries (Northern latitudes, Australia)
Environment	No evidence found
Diet	No evidence found
Behavior	No evidence found
Comorbidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asthma, especially severe asthma, is a risk factor for more frequent anaphylaxis.[84] This is shown for all ages and both males and females – see Table 5.1 UK data by Gonzalez-Perez et al.[47]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mastocytosis[87, 89] includes a group of hematopoietic neoplasms named for the main site(s) of pathological increase in mast cell number, described in a-c below. WHO has established major and minor diagnostic criteria based on extracutaneous biopsy showing multifocal aggregates of mast cells, demonstration of a KIT codon 816 mutation, or presence of mast cell clones expressing CD117 with CD25 or CD2 in bone marrow, blood or other extracutaneous organs and baseline serum tryptase persistently $\geq 20\text{ng/mL}$ [90]. All conditions are rare but incidence data are scarce. Cohen et al, who claimed to have done the first population-based epidemiologic study of mastocytosis, estimated the incidence of systemic mastocytosis in the Danish population to be 0.89/100,000/year [91]. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Cutaneous mastocytosis: increased skin mastocytes b. Systemic mastocytosis: mastocytes increased in one or more sites other than skin (gastrointestinal tract, bone marrow, liver, spleen, lymph nodes, other) c. Mast cell sarcoma: arising in bone, muscle, fat, connective tissue or blood vessels. Mast cell activation disorders include all types of mastocytosis with increased number of mast cells, as well as conditions with hyperactive mast cells or increased basal serum tryptase (see hereditary alpha-tryptasemia in Genetic factors above). One type, Monoclonal mast cell activation syndrome, characterized by recurrent episodes of anaphylaxis with hypotension and syncope, is most often initiated by insect stings and less commonly by food or drugs.[87] It is beyond the scope of this guide to present more detail on this complex subject. An editorial by Valent et al [92] provides an overview of the very active ongoing research efforts to classify and manage mast cell disorders.
Iatrogenic/Injury/Trauma	No evidence found
Infection	No evidence found
Medication	No evidence found
Toxin/Toxic exposures	No evidence found
Vaccine	No evidence found
Other	No evidence found

TABLE 3.3. RISK FACTORS FOR SEVERE, INCLUDING FATAL ANAPHYLAXIS While there is not a consensus definition of severe anaphylaxis most studies use the one or more of the following outcomes as indicative of severe anaphylaxis: admission to hospital or ICU, prolonged stay in hospital, need for intubation, fatal outcome. The prevalence of such outcomes will vary by study, but in one large USA study, among 38,695 patients seen in emergency rooms from 2005 – 2014 for anaphylaxis: 11.5% were hospitalized, 5.3% were admitted to ICU, 1.5% needed intubation and 0.45% had a near fatal episode (defined by occurrence of tracheostomy, respiratory arrest or cardiac arrest). [17]

Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> infants[68, 84, 93] (where recognition can be more difficult) and elderly[68, 85]
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A European Registry study of 8055 anaphylaxis patients across 11 countries found that the odds of having a severe anaphylactic event increased with each year of age by 1.6% (95% CI 1.4-1.9%) [94]. A USA study of risk factors for anaphylaxis deaths found the highest rate in 75-84 year olds (2.04/million), and the relative risk was 19.5 (95% CI 15.3-24.9) when compared to children ≤17 years of age who had the lowest rate (0.1/million). [95] Another USA study multivariate analysis correlated age ≥65 years with severe outcome (OR 3.15; 95% CI 2.88-3.44). The same study showed an independent correlation with presence of cardiac disease (OR 1.56; 1.50-1.63) or lung disease (OR 1.23; 1.16-1.30). • Several factors likely contribute to the increased severity and mortality in the elderly population including: higher prevalence of comorbidities including hypertension, cardiac and cerebrovascular disease, arrhythmias, polypharmacy, limited compensatory mechanisms in the face of acute events as well as delayed recognition and treatment due to decreased frequency of skin manifestations in anaphylaxis. [96] • Increased age plus concomitant mastocytosis (OR 3.1; 95% CI 2.6-3.7) [94]
Sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased severity of anaphylaxis: male sex (OR 1.2; 95% CI 1.1-1.3)[94] pregnancy, menses[84]
Genetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hereditary alpha-tryptasemia, an autosomal dominant genetic trait found in 5% of Caucasians. [86, 88] Increased severity demonstrated primarily among individuals with anaphylaxis triggered by stinging insects, but has also been found to correlate with severe food-triggered anaphylaxis in children. Reviewed in Wu et al. [86]
Pregnancy	No evidence found
Pre-/Peri-/Post-Natal Condition	No evidence found
Social/Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychological burden: OR 1.4 (95% CI 1.2-1.6) [94]
Occupation	No evidence found
Season	No evidence found
Geo-location	No evidence found
Environment	No evidence found
Diet	No evidence found
Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vigorous physical exercise: OR 1.5(95% CI 1.3-1.7) [94]
Comorbidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asthma, especially severe asthma, is associated with a greater frequency of anaphylactic shock (see UK data by Gonzalez-Perez et al [47] in Table 5.1). • Mast cell disorders: see detailed description in Table 3.2 above. The presentation of anaphylaxis in individuals with systemic mastocytosis more commonly includes hypotension with loss of consciousness, flushing and abdominal cramping than the more typical skin and respiratory symptoms and signs. [68, 87] • thyroid disease • cardiovascular disease[96]

Injury	No evidence found
Infection	No evidence found
Medication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anaphylaxis triggered by any medication (OR 1.50; 1.38-1.63)[17] • antihypertensive medications (beta-adrenergic blockers, calcium channel blockers, ACE inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, direct renin inhibitors)[81] • intake of beta blockers (OR 1.9; 95% CI 1.5-2.2) or ACE inhibitors (OR 1.28; 945% CI 1.05-1.51) in temporal proximity to allergen exposure [94] • NSAIDS, proton pump inhibitors[96]
Toxin/Toxic Exposures	No evidence found
Vaccine	No evidence found
Anaphylaxis related mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Japanese study looked at the epidemiology of out of hospital cardiac arrests (OHCA) caused by anaphylaxis. The annual overall incidence of OHCA was 115.4/100,000 population and of these 0.03% were anaphylaxis related [97]. Specific causes of death were airway obstruction, circulatory insufficiency, bronchoconsstriction and hypoxemia. • Perez-Codesido et al did a systematic review of observational studies on the incidence of fatal anaphylaxis. [98] 46 studies were included (15 North America, 22 Europe, 3 South America, 3 Asia, 2 Australia, 1 Africa). Overall, mortality for all causes of anaphylaxis was 0.002-2.51 deaths/million person years. There was a large degree of heterogeneity across all studies. Those interested in country specific rates can consult the publication.

Table 3.4 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with Measles containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
Cohort study (n=3)								
Esteghamati, 2011[99]	Iran	2006	12 months & 4-6 years	2	MMR	Incidence per 100,000 children or 100,000 doses (95% CI)	4.6 (0.6-16.6)	Case ascertainment= AEFIs to MMR vaccinations were defined based on World Health Organization (WHO) definitions Vaccinated n = 43,447
			12 months	1			7.1 (1.8-39.5)	

			4-6 years	1			3.4 (0.9-19.0)	
Klein, 2015[100]	USA	2000 – 2012	12-23 months	2	MMRV	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	1.68	Case ascertainment = ICD-9 codes Risk period = 0 days Number of doses: MMRV= 123,200 MMR+V= 584,987
				5	MMR+V		0.85	
Khetsuriani, 2010[101]	Georgia	2008 - 2009	Median: 13 years	1	MR	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.20	Case ascertainment= Causality assessment Vaccinated n = 50 Number of doses = About 493,000
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=11)								
Vahdani, 2005[102]	Iran	2003 - 2004	-	1	MR	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.049	Number of doses = 2,049,170
Patja, 2000[103]	Finland	1982 - 1996	-	14	MMR	Incidence per 100,000 doses	0.5	Vaccinated n = 1,800,000 Number of doses = 2,990,000
Meng, 2017[104]	China	2009 - 2014	-	3	MR	Annual incidence rate, per 100,000 doses*	0.08	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3
				3	MMR		0.08	
				7	Measles		0.57	
				1	MM		0.13	
Shu, 2011[105]	China	2007 - 2008	-	1	Measles	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses administered*	0.025	Vaccinated n = 3,980,978
D'Souza, 2000[106]	Australia	1998 - 1999	4-13 years	1	MMR	Rate per 100,000 doses	0.06	Case ascertainment= Pan-American Health Organization
Patja, 2001[107]	Finland	1982 - 1996	14 months - 23 years	30	MMR	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	1	Risk period = 9 hours Vaccinated n = 1.8 million Number of doses = 2,990,000
Su, 2019[108]	USA	1990 - 2016	Median: 12 years	206	MMR	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.11	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 & MeDRA Risk period = 1 day

								Vaccinated n = 467,960
Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	1,145	MMR	Reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	1.83 (1.73-1.94)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0 Vaccinated n = 226,915
Erlewyn-Lajeunesse, 2012[110]	Multiple countries	2008 - 2009	Under 16 years	2	Measles	Incidence per 100,000 doses	12	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 120 mins
Oberle, 2016[111]	Germany	2008 - 2010	2 months - 17 years	1	Measles	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	12.76	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses = 9,404
Sakaguchi, 2000[112]	Japan	1994 - 1997	Mean (SD): 1 year 10 month (11 month)	111	Measles	Minimum estimate of the incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.684	Number of doses = 3,507,090
Other Studies (n=1)								
Bino, 2003[113]	Albania	2000	1-14 years	1	Measles -rubella	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.115	Case ascertainment = WHO guidelines Number of doses = 867,000

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

Table 3.5 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with COVID-19 vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=3)								
Wan, 2022[114]	China	2021 - 2022	Mean (SD):	1 st dose: 1	CoronaVac	Incidence rate ratio (95% CI)	0.42 (0.06–2.86)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9-CM Risk period = 2 days Vaccinated n: 1 st dose= 126,736
				2 nd dose: 5			2.61 (1.08-6.31)	

			70.4 years (8.1)					2 nd dose= 384,056
Torabi, 2022[115]	UK	-	-	1 st dose: -	ChAdOx1	Incidence rate ratio, during the 0-7 day risk period compared to the baseline period (95% CI)	11.87 (6.56-21.47)	Risk period = 28 days; divided in intervals: 0-7, 8-14, 15-21, 22-28 days Vaccinated n = 36,136
				2 nd dose: -			3.23 (1.15-9.04)	
				1 st dose: -	BNT162b2		33.3 (14.08-78.76)	
				2 nd dose: -			14.62 (4.56-46.85)	
				3 rd dose: -			9.80 (1.62-59.35)	
Copland, 2024[116]	UK	2020 - 2022	-	1 st dose: 40	BNT162b2	Incidence rate ratio among 18-24 year olds, compared to baseline period (95% CI)	1.02 (0.72-1.45)	Number of doses: BNT162b2 1 st dose: 3,131,742 2 nd dose: 2,823,984 3 rd dose: 1,502,039 mRNA-1273 3 rd dose: 738,020 ChAdOx1 1 st dose: 545,345 2 nd dose: 520,252
				2 nd dose: 30			0.98 (0.66-1.44)	
				3 rd dose: 16			1.00 (0.57-1.74)	
				3 rd dose: 6	mRNA-1273		1.06 (0.45-2.48)	
				1 st dose: 19	ChAdOx1		1.29 (0.76-2.16)	
				2 nd dose: 20			1.26 (0.76-2.09)	
Case Control (n=1)								
Imai, 2022[117]	Japan	2021	≤35 - >65 years	2	mRNA	Incidence rate per 100,000 doses*	0.2	Case ascertainment= BC Vaccinated n = 614,151 Number of doses = 1,201,688
Cohort study (n=5)								
Macy, 2022[118]	USA	2020 - 2021	-	2	mRNA	Rate (per 100,000 doses*) after receipt of the first dose	0.329	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Vaccinated n = 391,022 Number of doses = 606,273
TanJTC, 2021[119]	Singapore	2021	Median (IQR): 22 (20-30) years	2	mRNA	Incidence per 100,000 doses	1.6	Vaccinated n = 64,661 Number of doses = 127, 081

Halder, 2022[120]	Australia	2021	Mean (SD): 40.6 years	2	BNT162b2	Incidence	0.003%	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 2 Number of doses = 57,842
Wong, 2022[121]	China	2021	18+ years	1 st dose: 27	BNT162b2	Cumulative incidence (events/100,000 doses)	2.06	Case ascertainment= ICD-9-CM Vaccinated n = BNT162b2 1 st dose: 1,308,820 2 nd dose: 1,116,677 CoronaVac 1 st dose: 955,859 2 nd dose: 821,560
				2 nd dose: 13			1.16	
				1 st dose: 7	CoronaVac		0.73	
				2 nd dose: 3			0.37	
Blumenthal, 2021[122]	USA	2020 - 2021	Mean (SD): 41 years (13)	16	mRNA	Incidence rate per 100,000 vaccinations of first dose	24.7	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 3 days Vaccinated n = 64,900 Number of doses = 64,900
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=22)								
Klein, 2021[123]	USA	2020 - 2021	Mean (SD): 49 years	30	BNT162b2	Confirmed cases per 100,000 doses*	0.48	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1 day Vaccinated n = 10,162,227 Number of doses = 11,845,128
				25	MRNA-1273		0.51	
Inokuma, 2023[124]	USA	2020-2021	-	55	Pfizer & Moderna	Verified incidence rates (per 100,000 doses*)	0.5	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses USA: 1,893,360 Japan: 578,835
	Japan			509			0.3	
Singh, 2022[125]	USA	2021	Mean (SD): 50.7 years (17.85)	297	BNTb262	Frequency following administration COVID-19 vaccine (per 100,000 doses*)	0.234	Case ascertainment= MedDRA, version 24.0 Vaccinated n = 141,208 Number of doses = 239,970,000
				392	mRNA-1273		0.375	
				58	JNJ-78436735		0.705	
Urdaneta, 2024[126]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2022	<2 - ≥75 years	2588	mRNA-1273	Observed-to-expected ratios comparing observed	2.09 (1.93–2.25)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Risk period = 3 days Number of doses = 772,908,958

						rates background/ expected rate (95% CI)		
Shivarev, 2023[127]	Australia	2021	Median (IQR): 50 years	8	Adenovirus	Rate per 100,000 doses*	1.59	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 42 days Number of doses: Adenovirus = 501,821 Pfizer mRNA = 225,929
				4	Pfizer mRNA		1.77	
Lloyd, 2022[128]	USA	2020 - 2022	12-64 years	Optum: 20 Healthcore: 33 CVS: 20	mRNA1273	Rate Ratio comparing incidence of observed events compared to adjusted historical background rates	Optum: 7.64 Healthcore: 11.88 CVS: 12.40	Case ascertainment= ICD-10-CM
				Optum: 26 Healthcore: 42 CVS: 39	BNT162b2		Optum: 4.48 Healthcore: 7.50 CVS: 10.86	
				Optum: <11 Healthcore: <11 CVS: <11	Ad26.COV 2.S		Optum: 4.05 Healthcore: 10.47 CVS: 20.41	
Gallo, 2022[129]	Australia	2021 - 2022	Median (IQR): 27 years (19.0)	7	AZD1222	Approximate rate per 100,000* vaccines administered	4.325	Case ascertainment= MedRA Number of doses = 977,559
				15	mRNA- 1273		2.918	
				1	BNT162b2		0.387	
Hwang, 2021[130]	South Korea	2021	Median (Range): 37 years (17–91)	296	ChAdOx1	Rate per 100,000* vaccines administered	0.42	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Number of doses = 78,416,802
				790	BNT162b2		0.66	
				144	CX-024414		0.43	
				48	Ad26.COV 2.S		1.41	
Toledo- Salinas, 2022[131]	Mexico	2020 - 2021	Mean (SD): 41 years (11)	35	BNT162b2	Unadjusted incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.229	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Number of doses = 61,414,803
				6	mRNA- 1273		0.528	
				13	ChAdOx1		0.052	

				8	Ad5-nCoV		0.136	
				2	rAd26-rAd5		0.060	
				2	CoronaVac		0.021	
Peter, 2022[132]	South Africa	2021	Median (IQR): 50 years (45-53)	4	Ad26.COV 2.S	Overall prevalence following single dose per 100,000 doses*	0.84	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 14 days Number of doses = 477,234
Barth, 2023[133]	Germany	2020 - 2022	-	243	Comirnaty	Reporting rates per 100,000 vaccinations	0.19	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 24 hours
				20	Spikevax		0.07	
				46	Vaxzevria		0.36	
				5	Jcovden		0.14	
				2	Nuvaxovid		2.5	
Amarasinghe, 2023[134]	Multiple countries	2021 - 2022	-	-	BNT162b2	Reporting rates~ per 100,000 doses*	13.7	Number of doses = 732.3 million ~ Rates include suspected and confirmed cases
					mRNA-1273		0.89	
					AZD1222		0.99	
					Ad26.COV 2.S		0.56	
					Gam-Covid-Vac		0.16	
					CoronaVac		0.15	
					BBIBP-CorV		0.03	
Boufidou, 2023[135]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2023	-	Anaphylactic reactions: 12,549	COVID-19	Incidence of per 100,000 doses*	0.896	Case ascertainment= BC & MedDRA Number of doses = 1,401,107,098
				Anaphylactic shock: 2,039			0.146	
Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	mRNA= 16,416	COVID-19	Reported odds ratio compared to all	1.89 (1.85-1.92)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0

				Inactivated = 830		other vaccines (95% CI)	2.21 (2.06-2.37)	Vaccinated n: mRNA= 4009826 Inactivated= 162570
Lee, 2023[136]	South Korea	2021 - 2022	-	112	ChAdOx1-S	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.55	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 30 minutes Number of doses = 125,107,883
				597	BNT162b2		0.76	
				129	mRNA-1273		0.52	
				30	Ad26.COV 2.S		1.99	
				6	NVX-CoV2373		1.11	
Romantowski, 2024[137]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2023	-	-	Spikevax	Incidence rate per 100,000 doses	0.254	Number of doses = 981,454,243
					Comirnaty		0.367	
					CHADOX1		0.645	
					AD26.COV 2.S		0.666	
					NVX-CoV2373		2.663	
					Valneva		44.307	
Maltezou, 2023[138]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2022	0-17 years	18	mRNA-1273	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	1.214	Number of doses = 28,512,812
				353	BNT162b2		1.284	
Kim, 2024[139]	South Korea	-	12-17 years	515	COVID-19	Adjusted reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	0.86 (0.72-1.02)	Vaccinated n = 80,018
CDC, 2021[140]	USA	2020	Media (IQR): 40 years (27-60)	21	BNT162b2	Rate per 100,000 doses*	1.11	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Risk period = 1 day Number of doses = 1,893,360
	Japan	2021		581	BNT162b2		0.4	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3

Yamaguchi, 2022[141]			10 - >80 years	50	mRNA-1273	Cases per 100,000* vaccinations	0.16	
Lee, 2021[142]	South Korea	2021	Median (IQR): 37 years (21-84)	33	Vaxzevria	Confirmed cases per 100,000 doses*	1.82	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Number of doses: Vaxzevria = 1,810,255 Comirnaty = 1,779,553
				11	Comirnaty		0.62	
Desai, 2021[143]	USA	2020 - 2021	Mean (SD): 46 years (16)	114	Pfizer	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	0.58	Vaccinated n = 12,630 Number of doses = 36,819,212
				39	Moderna		0.23	
Meta-analyses (n=3)								
Alhumaid, 2021[144]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2021	-	-	COVID-19	Pooled prevalence per 1,000,000 doses administered (95% CI)	8.0 (0-11.3)	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Vaccinated n = 26,337,421
				-			2.8 (0.0-5.7)	
Greenhawt, 2023[145]	Multiple countries	-	-	674	COVID-19	Incidence per 1,000,000 doses (95% CI)	7.91 (4.02-15.59)	Case ascertainment= BC Vaccinated n = 57,089,598
				-	Adenovirus vector	Odds ratio following vaccine compared to mRNA vaccines (95% CI)	0.47 (0.33-0.68)	
					Inactivated		0.31 (0.18-0.53)	
Sobczak, 2022[146]	Multiple countries	-	-	-	COVID-19	Overall risk ratio of anaphylaxis or anaphylactic reaction compared to unvaccinated people (95% CI)	106.99 (39.95-286.57)	-
					Ad26.COV 2.S	Risk ratio of anaphylaxis or anaphylactic reactions compared	209 (95% CI: 29.3-1490.67, I2=0%)	
					mRNA-1273		62.89 (95% CI: 14.08-280.84, I2=55%)	

					BNT162b2	to unvaccinated people (95% CI	133.93 (95% CI: 22.88-783.90)	
					ChAdOx1 nCoV-19		176.64 (95% CI: 1.00-31280.66)	

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

Table 3.6 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with Influenza vaccines, by study type

Author, year,	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=3)								
McCarthy, 2013[147]	USA	2009 – 2011	-	2009-2010: 9	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent	Incidence rate ratio of pre-specified claims-identified anaphylaxis compared with the historical cohort (95% CI)	28.55 (3.57-228.44)	Number of doses = 3,508,144
				2010-2011: 3	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent		6.70 (0.60-74.74)	
Daley, 2018[148]	USA	2003 – 2013	Mean (SD): 8.7 years (4.3)	1	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent	Adjusted incident rate ratio based upon cases confirmed by manual medical record review (95% CI)	19.98 (1.73-230.29)	Risk period = 0-2 days Number of doses = 590,018
Shi, 2024[149]	USA	2022 - 2023	-	76	Any Quadrivalent	Incidence rate ratio in the seasonality-adjusted and PPV-based imputation analysis (95% CI)	2.40 (0.96-6.03)	Risk period = 0-1 days Number of doses = 12.7 million
				46	High-Dose Quadrivalent inactivated		2.31 (0.67-7.91)	
				24	Quadrivalent adjuvanted		3.28 (0.71-15.08)	
Cohort study (n=6)								

Kawai, 2014[150]	USA	2012 - 2013	>6 Months	7	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent	Relative risk of anaphylaxis compared to historical controls (95% CI)	1.3 (0.5, 3.1)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 0-2 days Number of doses = 3,303,339
Goud, 2021[151]	USA	2015 - 2019	65 - ≥ 90 years	-	Influenza	Incidence Rate per 100,000 person-years (95% CI)	8.24 (5.74, 11.84)	Case ascertainment= BC 1-3 Risk period = 2 days Vaccinated n = 61,182,106
						Incidence Rate per 100,000* Doses/Visits (95% CI)	0.068 (0.047, 0.097)	
Yih, 2016[152]	USA	2013 - 2014	≥6 months	15	IIV	Relative risk compared to historical rates	0.63	Risk period = 0-1 days Number of doses = 6,682,336
Layton, 2020[153]	USA	2010 - 2016	-	23	Trivalent or quadrivalent	Crude incidence rate per 100,000* person years	1.6	Number of doses: Trivalent or quadrivalent=481,974 Trivalent = 364,264
				20	Trivalent		1.8	
Moro, 2013[154]	Italy	2009 - 2010	-	-	Inactivated	Incidence rate per 100,000 doses	0.8	Vaccinated n = 127,552
McNeil, 2016[74]	USA	2009 - 2021	4-65 years	10	Trivalent inactivated	Incidence per 1 100,000 doses*	0.135	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Number of doses: Trivalent = 7,434,628 Monovalent = 1,090,279
				2	Monovalent inactivated		0.183	
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=16)								
Vellozzi, 2010[155]	USA	2009 - 2010	Median: 26 years	101	Inactivated H1N1	Reporting rate anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses*	0.16	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 82.4 million
				15	Attenuated H1N1		0.09	
Banzhoff, 2011[156]	Multiple countries	2009 - 2010	Median: 44 years	43	Inactivated H1N1v	Reporting rate by person years	65.4 / 100,000	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses = 12 million
Haber, 2015[157]	USA	2013 - 2014	Median: 32 years	1	LAIV4	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.0079	Case ascertainment = BC Number of doses = 12.7 million

Ropero-Álvarez, 2015[158]	Multiple countries	2009 - 2010	-	76	H1N1 pandemic vaccine	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.053	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 144,621,593
Tavares, 2011[159]	Multiple countries	2010	Median: 30 years	73	Pandemrix	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses ⁸ administered	0.18	Case ascertainment= BC 1-2 Number of doses: Pandemrix = 142 million Arepanrix = 137 million
			Median: 34 years	24	Arepanrix		0.20	
Moro, 2015[160]	USA	2013 - 2015	Median: 18.5 years	2	Inactivated / Flucelvax	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses* distributed	0.04	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3, MedDRA Number of doses = ~ 5.6 million
Moro, 2013[161]	USA	2011 - 2013	4-88 years	8	TIV-ID	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	0.17	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 + physician diagnosis Risk period = 2 days Number of doses = ~4.7 million
Moro, 2020[162]	USA	2011 - 2019	≥65 years	13	IIV-HD	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.0115	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3, MedDRA Number of doses = 113.1 million
Gattas, 2018[163]	Brazil	2013 - 2017	-	75	TIV	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.047	Number of doses = 158,735,729
Haber, 2015[157]	USA	2013-2014	-	1	LAIV4	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.0079	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 12.7 million
Giang, 2024[164]	Canada	2021 - 2022	Median: 52 years	6	IIV3-Adj, IIVD4-SD, IIV4-HD, IIV4-cc, LAIV-4	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	40.81	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Number of doses = 15,605,176
Su, 2019[108]	USA	2010 – 2016	Median 12 years	254	Influenza	Rate of anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses* that met the BC case definition (range)	0.03 (0.02-0.08)	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 1 day Vaccinated n = 467,960

Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	2,393	Influenza	Reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	2.36 (2.27-2.46)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0 Vaccinated n = 368,978
Rouleau, 2013[165]	Canada	2009	Mean (SD): 34.1 (22.4)	32	AS03- adjuvanted H1N1	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	0.8	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 1 hour Number of doses = 4,199,866
Nakayama, 2007[166]	Japan	-	-	19	Gelatin free vaccine	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.058	Number of doses shipped: Influenza Gel. = 32.86 million Influenza G.T. = 2.46 million
				3	Gelatin, thimerosal free vaccine		0.122	
Oberle, 2016[111]	Germany	2008 - 2010	2 months - 17 years	8	Pandemic H1N1	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	1.18	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses = 928,500

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

Table 3.7 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with HPV vaccines, by study type

Author, year, Journal	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
Cohort study (n=2)								
Gee, 2011[167]	USA	2006 – 2009	9-26 years	1	HPV4	Rate per million doses (95% CI)	1.7 (0.04-9.3)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 0-2 days Number of doses = 600,558
Cameron, 2016[168]	UK	2004 – 2014	12-18 years	Females = 7 Males = 6	HPV	2012 Incidence ratio (Observed/Expected * 100), 95% CI	Females = 79.4 (31.8-163.6) Males = 91.5 (33.4-199.2)	Vaccinated n (2012) Females = 206,323 Males = 216,88
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=9)								
	Australia	2007		Overall=7			2.6 (1.0-5.3)	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2

Brotherton, 2008[169]			12-26 years	After 1 st dose=5	Gardasil	Rate of anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses (95% CI)	5.3 (1.7-12.3)	Number of doses = 269,680
				After 2 nd dose=2			2.2 (0.3-7.9)	
Phillips, 2020[170]	Australia	2007 - 2017	12-26 years	30	HPV4	Reporting rate for anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses	0.32	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = All cases occurred on the day of vaccination Number of doses = ~ 9.4 million
Dalla Valle, 2024[171]	Italy	-	≥ 9	1	HPV9 HPV4	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses (95% CI)	0.15	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1 Risk period = Within 1-hour Vaccinated n = 469
Harris, 2014[172]	Canada	2007 – 2011	12-15 years	2	HPV4	Rate for anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses distributed	0.3	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 691,994
Hu, 2021[173]	China	2018 - 2020	-	2	HPV4	Reporting odds ratio (ROR) for anaphylaxis following HPV vaccine compared to all other vaccines	0.38	Case ascertainment= ICD- 10 preferred terms Vaccinated n = 238 Number of doses = 889,282
Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	608	HPV	Reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	1.64 (1.51-1.78)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0 Vaccinated n = 134,328
Erlewyn-Lajeunesse, 2012[110]	Multiple countries	2008 - 2009	<16 years	3	Bivalent	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.14	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 120 mins
Oberle, 2016[111]	Germany	2008 – 2010	2 months - 17 years	3	Bivalent and Quadrivalent	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.223	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses = 1,406,289
Slade, 2009[174]	US	2006 – 2008	-	-	Quadrivalent	Rate for anaphylaxis per 100,000 doses distributed	0.1	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 23,051,336

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

Table 3.8 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with pneumococcal vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=2)								
Kim, 2024[175]	South Korea	2018 – 2022	Mean: 10 months	2	PCV10 or PCV13	Adjusted IRR (95 % CI)	0.23 (0.05–1.10)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 0-2 days Vaccinated n = 8,661
Yoon, 2024[176]	South Korea	2022 – 2023	Mean: 72.44 years	-	PPSV23	Incidence rate ratio compared to the control interval (95% CI)	0.30 (0.04-2.21)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 28 days Vaccinated n = 4,355
Cohort study (n=3)								
Tseng, 2018[177]	USA	2011 – 2015	≥65 years	5	PCV13	Adjusted IRR compared to PPSV23 (95% CI)	1.32 (95% CI: 0.30–5.79)	Risk period = 1 day Vaccinated n = 545,727
McNeil, 2016[74]	USA	2009 - 2021	4-65 years	1	PPSV23	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.248	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Vaccinated n = 403,803
Goud, 2021[151]	USA	2015 - 2019	65 - ≥ 90 years	-	Pneumococcal^	Incidence Rate per 100,000 person-years (95% CI)	14.08 (8.27, 23.96)	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 2-days Vaccinated n = 61,182,106
						Incidence Rate per 100,000 doses*/visits	0.116	
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=5)								
Wise, 2004[178]	USA	2000 - 2002	-	14	PCV7	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	~0.044	Number of doses = ~ 31.5 million

Hu, 2022[179]	China	2017 - 2020	-	12	PCV13	Reporting odds ratio, compared to other vaccines	0.91	Number of doses = 1,895,548
						Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	0.6	
Su, 2019[108]	USA	1990 - 2016	Median: 12 years	21	PPSV23	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.03	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 1 day Vaccinated n = 467,960
Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	1,070	Pneumococcal^	Reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	1.41 (1.33-1.50)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0 Vaccinated n = 274,186
Oberle, 2016[111]	Germany	2008 - 2010	2 months - 17 years	4	PCV7, PCV10	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.09	Case ascertainment = BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses = 4,827,653

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

^ All pneumococcal vaccines included

Table 3.9 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with yellow fever vaccine, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=6)								
Rojas, 2023[180]	USA	2017 - 2021	-	1	Yellow fever live attenuated	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses*	0.016	Vaccinated n = 627,079 Number of doses = 627,079
Cottin, 2013[181]	Multiple countries	1993 - 2010	-	33	Yellow fever live attenuated	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	0.01	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Number of doses = 276,000,000

McClenathan, 2024[182]	USA	1999 - 2018	2-63 years	111	Yellow fever	Incidence rate per 100,000 doses*	1.46	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Number of doses = 7,624,160
Lindsey, 2008[183]	USA	2000 - 2006	6-55 years	33	Yellow fever	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	2.2	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Risk period = 4 hours Number of doses = 1,534,170
Lindsey, 2016[184]	USA	2007 - 2014	2-63 years	30	Yellow fever	Reporting rate per 100,000 administered	1.4	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Risk period = 2 days Number of doses = 2,224,790
Kelso, 1999[185]	USA	1990 - 1997	-	22	Yellow fever	Reporting rate per 238,000 doses administered	1	Risk period = Probable anaphylactic reactions: 4 hours; Possible anaphylactic reactions: >4 hours Number of doses = 5,236,820

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

Table 3.10 Studies reporting on risk of anaphylaxis after vaccination with other vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group	Number of anaphylaxis cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
Cohort study (n=4)								
Huang, 2020[186]	China	2012 - 2017	Mean (SD): 4.8 (6.2) years	1	DTaP	Incidence rate per 100,000 person-years (95% CI)	14.6 (2.1–103.4)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 7-days Number of doses: DTaP = 365,707 H. influenzae = 108,823
				1	Oral polio		18.8 (2.7–133.7)	
				1	H. influenzae		50.0 (7.0–354.3)	
Dobson, 1995[187]	Canada	1992 - 1993	10-12 years	1	Engerix-B	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses*	0.782	Number of doses = 127,922
Goud, 2021[151]	USA	2015 – 2019	65 - ≥ 90 years	-	Zoster	Incidence Rate per 100,000	17.13 (5.89, 49.83)	Case ascertainment= BC LOC1-3 Risk period = 2-days

						person-years (95% CI)		Vaccinated n = 61,182,106
						Incidence Rate per 100,000* Doses/Visits*	0.141	
McNeil, 2016[74]	USA	2009 - 2021	4-65 years	1	Tdap	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.051	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Number of doses: Tdap = 1,951,153 Hepatitis A = 296,271 Zoster = 208, 407 Rabies = 11,619
				1	Hepatitis A		0.338	
				2	Zoster		0.960	
				1	Rabies		8.61	
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=15)								
Walker, 2018[188]	USA	2012 - 2016	Median (Range): 32 years (5-79)	1	JEV	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	0.1	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Number of doses = 802,229
Monteiro, 2010[189]	Brazil	2003 - 2004	Mean, months: 3.8	-	DTwP-Hib	Incidence rates per 100,000 doses administered	1 st dose: 0.1	Number of doses = 18,700,000
							2 nd dose: 0.1	
Moro, 2016[190]	USA	1990 - 2015	Media (IQR): 32 years	7	Imovax Rabies	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.184	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Number of doses = 3.8 million
Pan, 2022[191]	China	2015 - 2020	-	2	DTaP-IPV/Hib	Reporting odds ratio compared to other vaccines	0.7	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Number of doses = 2,860,884
Miller, 2018[192]	USA	2006 - 2015	50-79 years	11	Herpes zoster live attenuated	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses* distributed	0.05	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 or physician diagnosis Number of doses = 21,846,030

Okuno, 2022[193]	Japan	2013 - 2017	0-1 years	6	BCG	Incidence per 100,000 doses* administered	0.16	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3
Shaum, 2022[194]	Zimbabwe	-	Media (IQR): 3 years (2, 9)	1	Typhoid conjugate vaccine	Rate per 100,000 doses administered	0.31	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 42 days
Chang, 2013[195]	USA	2005 - 2007	Media (IQR): 15 years (9-38)	12	Tdap	Rate per 100,000 doses	0.06	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 16 hours Number of doses = ~ 20 million
Chaves, 2008[196]	USA	1995 - 2005	-	27	Varicella-zoster virus	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	0.1	Number of doses = ~ 48 million
Lindsey, 2010[197]	USA	1999 - 2009	20-44 years	11	JEV	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	0.9	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-2 Risk period = 2 hours Number of doses = 1,262,840
Su, 2019[108]	USA	2006 - 2016	Median: 12 years	39	Varicella-zoster virus	Rate per 100,000 doses*	0.21	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 1 day Vaccinated n = 467,960
Lee, 2024[109]	Multiple countries	1967 - 2023	-	18	Cholera	Reported odds ratio compared to all other vaccines (95% CI)	2.65 (1.67-4.21)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA version 25.0 Vaccinated n: Cholera = 2,467 DTaP-IPV-Hib = 812,141 Meningococcal = 150,715 Typhoid = 17,021 Encephalitis = 20,806 Hepatitis A = 63,173 Hepatitis B = 110,384 Rotavirus = 82,471 TB = 34,441 Zoster = 216,070
				3,008	DTaP-IPV-Hib		1.34 (1.29-1.39)	
				500	Meningococcal^		1.20 (1.10-1.31)	
				203	Typhoid		4.35 (3.79-5.00)	
				187	Encephalitis~		3.27 (2.83-3.78)	
				424	Hepatitis A		2.44 (2.21-2.68)	
				816	Hepatitis B		2.69 (2.51-2.88)	
				331	Rotavirus		1.45 (1.30-1.62)	
				91	TB		0.95 (0.78-1.17)	
				372	Zoster		0.62 (0.56-0.69)	

Oberle, 2016[111]	Germany	2008 – 2010	2 months - 17 years	1	Rubella	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	4.76	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3 Risk period = 48 hours Number of doses: Rubella = 25,225 Tick borne encephalitis = 3,125,546 Meningococcal C = 3,167,851 DTaP-IPV-Hib-HBV = 4,828,737
				2	TBE		0.069	
				1	Meningococcal conjugate		0.04	
				3	DTaP-IPV-Hib-HBV		0.065	
Nakayama, 2007[166]	Japan	-	-	2	JEV porcine gelatin vaccine	Incidence per 100,000 doses*	0.063	Number of doses shipped: JEV P-M = 4.78 million doses JEV G.T. = 1.45 million doses DPT Gel. = 9.68 million doses DPT G.T. = 0.88 million doses
				1	Gelatin, thimerosal free JEV vaccine		0.069	
				9	Gelatin free DPT vaccine		0.093	
				1	Gelatin, thimerosal free DPT vaccine		0.1148	
Sakaguchi, 2000[112]	Japan	1994 – 1997	Mean: 2 years 7 months	30	Varicella	Minimum estimate of the incidence per 100,000 doses*	1.03	-
			Mean: 2 years 8 months	17	Mumps		0.436	
				50	Rubella		0.731	

* Reported data adjusted to 100,000 doses

^ All meningococcal vaccines included

~ All encephalitis vaccines included

APPENDIX 4

Anaphylaxis Case Definition Key Caveats for Diagnosis, Data Analysis and Presentation

4.1. Anaphylaxis Case Definition[2] Key Caveats for Diagnosis, Data Analysis and Presentation

4.1.1 Key elements of Case Definition (CD)

- Case definition criteria predominantly based on clinical signs relying on assessment of dermatologic, cardiovascular, respiratory, gastrointestinal presentations and a single laboratory measurement (mast cell tryptase)
- Anaphylaxis V-2 relies primarily on objective evaluation by health care professionals, as opposed to more subjective reported symptoms
- The CD (LoC 1-3) is not a measure of anaphylaxis severity.
- **Required for all three levels** is an event time course characterized by ‘rapid progression’ with the time from first symptom or sign appearance to multi-system involvement required to be within one hour or less.
- The case definition is not intended to be used for clinical diagnosis or management. Treatment (usually with adrenaline/epinephrine) and response to treatment is not included in the case definition. Treatment is often given soon after the onset of symptoms.
- Comprehensive documentation of symptoms and objective signs during the course of presentation is critical to the application of the case definition. A **RAPID** Assessment form[198] included a checklist with all the major/minor criteria for anaphylaxis V-1. This is reproduced below, with the appropriate modifications to match Anaphylaxis V-2.

TABLE 4. Rapid assessment of possible post-immunisation cases of Anaphylaxis, based on V-2 of Brighton case definition.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be used if anaphylaxis is suspected because of rapid progression of symptoms and signs involving multiple systems including skin, mucosa, respiratory cardiovascular and gastrointestinal systems. • Do a RAPID assessment as described below, using the checklist in the right-hand column to record observations. Check all that are confirmed to be present: 			
R ash and mucosa	Present at a location other than the vaccine administration site:		<input type="checkbox"/> urticaria (hives) <input type="checkbox"/> angioedema (skin swelling)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Generalized redness of the skin with itch	<input type="checkbox"/> Generalized redness of the skin without itch	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Bilateral red and itchy eyes that is new in onset		
A irway and respiratory	Signs documented by healthcare professional with or without a stethoscope:		<input type="checkbox"/> expiratory wheeze <input type="checkbox"/> inspiratory stridor
	Upper airway swelling observed & documented by a healthcare professional:		<input type="checkbox"/> tongue <input type="checkbox"/> pharynx <input type="checkbox"/> uvula <input type="checkbox"/> larynx
	<input type="checkbox"/> Tachypnoea	<input type="checkbox"/> Cyanosis <input type="checkbox"/> Grunting <input type="checkbox"/> Chest wall retractions	<input type="checkbox"/> Increased use of accessory respiratory muscles
	<input type="checkbox"/> Measured hypoxia with oxygen saturations <90%		
New (not present before immunization) & persistent (recurring or episode ≥5 minutes:		<input type="checkbox"/> cough <input type="checkbox"/> sneezing <input type="checkbox"/> runny nose	
P ressure (blood) and consciousness	<input type="checkbox"/> Measured hypotension	Age ≥11 yrs: Systolic <90mmHg or diastolic <60 mm Hg Age < 11yrs: Systolic < the sum of: 70mm Hg + 2 times age(yrs)	<input type="checkbox"/> Loss of consciousness (do not check if the episode is brief, and self-resolving typical of a vasovagal reaction)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Elevated mast cell tryptase (defined as elevated above upper normal limit for testing lab or >1.2 X baseline mast cell tryptase + 2ng/L)		
D iarrhoea/vomiting	New onset (not present prior to immunization). Note if <12 months old must be ≥2 episodes:		<input type="checkbox"/> Vomiting <input type="checkbox"/> Diarrhoea

4.1.2 Recommendations for real time assessment

- **Objective Assessment of Signs and Symptoms:** Most cases of anaphylaxis occur within minutes to a few hours of immunization. See Table 4.1 above. This provides a ‘snapshot’ of the major and minor criteria included in Brighton Anaphylaxis V-2. This can be provided to clinical trial immunization providers as an aid for what should be documented in the immunization clinic during the episode. It can be appended to the AEFI report and used to assign a level of diagnostic certainty, following the logic provided in Appendix 5. This is not meant to guide treatment. Many of the criteria can rapidly be assessed by one staff member as others are providing treatment. It is especially important to have objective documentation, by a qualified healthcare professional, of urticaria, angioedema, upper airway swelling, expiratory wheeze, inspiratory stridor and hypotension
- **Age-related variation in presentation of anaphylaxis.** The following are recommended resources for investigating anaphylaxis in specific age groups:
 - **Infants:** two review articles [199, 200] examine the recognition, diagnosis and investigation of anaphylaxis in infants. Some key points include:
 - As in all anaphylaxis involvement of skin, respiratory, cardiovascular and gastrointestinal systems may occur, but may be misinterpreted because of their relative frequency in infants due to other causes (e.g., rash and respiratory problems in viral respiratory tract infections, frequency of diarrhea, colicky abdominal pain, spitting up after feeding).
 - Most common presenting features of anaphylaxis in infants include hives, profuse vomiting and respiratory difficulty. Cardiovascular compromise tends to be a late occurrence or may be missed if blood pressure is not measured.
 - The 2022 revised case definition noted that following oral administration of vaccine (e.g., rotavirus vaccine) there needs to be at least 2 separate episodes of vomiting or diarrhea to be considered a major criterion for the definition of anaphylaxis.
 - **Adolescents:** Connor et al[201] provide an overview of ‘idiopathic’ anaphylaxis in the adolescent, which they note should only be considered after an extensive review of known causes and mimic disorders. They review several different triggers providing the general frequency (rare versus common) in teenagers.
 - **Elderly:** in contrast to infants, elderly are more likely to present with cardiovascular compromise and may have no apparent skin involvement[96]
- **Mast cell tryptase** is a highly specific (PPV 98%)[202] **marker for anaphylaxis but lacks sensitivity (NPV 17%; PPV 93%) [85]**. Given the specificity it has been elevated from a minor criterion in V-1 to a major criterion in V-2. It is important to note, however, that:
 - Levels peak between 15 and 120 minutes from onset
 - Samples need to be taken within 6 hours of the event onset
 - Recommendation: determine which study sites are able to measure mast cell tryptase and include it if feasible in the early assessment of anaphylaxis
- **Postmortem findings –**
 - no pathognomonic features of anaphylaxis and therefore not a part of the case definition

- Post-mortem mast cell tryptase measurement may be helpful for investigating a death where anaphylaxis is a possible cause. Garland et al [203] reviewed the literature on the use of post-mortem tryptase in such settings and provide several useful recommendations for when to consider it and how to obtain the sample based on published evidence. Briefly it should be considered in settings where the clinical history is consistent with the definition of anaphylaxis, especially where the trigger was parenterally-administered, as would be the case for most vaccines. Sampling should be done as soon as possible following death using a standardised sampling technique: aspiration with needle and syringe from femoral vein after clamping (to prevent backflow from central venous blood). The review presents multiple studies relating to the threshold for what would be considered elevated tryptase.

4.1.3 Data Collection Guidelines

- Important to document history of allergy including to any prior vaccine, vaccine component or medication; as well as history of food allergy; allergic rhinitis; eczema; asthma.
- See table 4.1 checklist above. Also see appendix 5 for a case report form that could be used for retrospective data collection of possible cases.
- Document date/time of:
 - Onset (time post-immunization when first sign or symptom indicative of anaphylaxis occurred)
 - ⊖ first observation (date and/or time of first observed sign or symptom)
 - final outcome - choose the most accurate:
 - recovery to pre-immunization health status
 - spontaneous resolution
 - resolution with therapeutic intervention
 - persistence of the event
 - recurrence of the event (biphasic anaphylaxis; recurrence may be from 1–72 hours after initial event; wide range of frequency (<1%-20%⁴) depending on study)
 - sequelae (specify)
 - death
- Document treatment given for anaphylaxis (especially epinephrine, steroids, volume replacement, antihistamines) including date / time given
- Determine whether there were any exposures other than immunization for the 24-hour period before and after immunization (vis a vis other stimulus for anaphylaxis including food, venom, environmental toxins or allergens, drugs)

4.1.4 Data Analysis Guidelines (Primarily for the setting of a clinical trial; but could apply to a large retrospective cohort study or background incidence study)

- If few cases are reported in the trial the concrete time course should be analyzed for each including interval from immunization to onset
- Classify each case into one of 5 categories:
 - Meets the case definition at:

1. Level 1 of certainty
 2. Level 2 of certainty
 3. Level 3 of certainty
- Does not meet the case definition:
 4. Reported as a case of anaphylaxis with insufficient evidence to meet any level of case definition
 5. Not a case of anaphylaxis – (e.g., there is a clear alternate diagnosis such as myocardial infarction)
 - If there are many cases, they should be analyzed as the number and percentage that onset in each interval shown below:
 - <30 minutes after immunization
 - 30-≤60 minutes after immunization
 - 60 -≤90 minutes after immunization
 - 90-≤120 minutes after immunization
 - Hourly increments thereafter

4.1.5 **Data Presentation Guidelines** – see section 3.3 of the 2007 Case Definition (V-1) publication.[1]. The V-2 WG did not make any changes to the guidelines for data presentation.

APPENDIX 5

Anaphylaxis Data Abstraction & Interpretation Forms With Algorithms for Assessing Level of Certainty And a Glossary of Terms

5.1. Anaphylaxis Data Abstraction and Interpretation Form with algorithms for assessing level of certainty

The form is organized in a series of Steps presented as tables.

- **Step 1** guides the collection of data needed to meet the case definition criteria for anaphylaxis. Depending on the specific criterion, data are collected using two formats:
 - i. as mutually exclusive answers of YES, NO or UNKNOWN to a series of questions
 - ii. as a checklist of specific things that were noted to be present (i.e. YES) like signs or symptoms, or lab test results.

Relatively simple criteria used in the case definition may be defined directly in Step 1. Others may require formulae to define – as done in Step 2.

- **Step 2** uses some or all of the data entered in Step 1 to assign values (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) to each case definition criterion.
- **Step 3** is a small tabular summary of the assigned value (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) for each criterion in the case definition.
- **Step 4** provides a tabular algorithm to assign the level of certainty that meets the case definition (Level 1, 2 or 3) or that does not meet the case definition (Levels 4 and 5).
- A pictorial algorithm is presented that provides, in a single page, all the relevant criteria needed to meet the case definition and a flow diagram that shows the path to each level of diagnostic certainty depending on the criterion values.
- A Glossary of Terms is also included. Any terms defined in the glossary are yellow highlighted in the Step 1 data form.

Digital Transformation: For the digital version, in the Automated Brighton Classification (ABC) Tool users need to enter data into the online form for Step 1 only and an LOC will be provided (based on the information in Steps 2-4 which operate in the background of the Tool) along with a summary of the data entered. In addition, the pictorial algorithm will be provided so users can see how the LOC was derived based on data entered. In contrast, for the analog version, as here in the Companion Guide, users must complete all 4 steps in order to reach the LOC.

The data abstraction form (analog or digital versions) can be used in several settings:

- **Epidemiologic research:** As a case report form for data abstraction from a hospital/other institutional chart as part of epidemiologic studies or hypothesis testing studies for causal association between vaccine (s) and anaphylaxis.
- **Real world evidence studies:** Guide data collection for case validation (all or a subset) in studies where electronic health data were used for case identification based on selected medical codes (ICD9/10, SNOMEDCT, MedDRA).
- **Clinical vaccine trials:** Serve as a supplement to a clinical trial case report form that does not capture information specific to anaphylaxis; i.e., when anaphylaxis is not part of solicited safety information in the clinical trial. In such settings it may also serve as a guide for the type of data to be collected and investigations to be done should anaphylaxis occur as an unsolicited adverse event.

- Pharmacovigilance:** Most AEFI report forms, including the CIOMS AEFI form, allow for free text to describe an adverse event but are not set up to collect specific information that would facilitate applying a standard Brighton case definition. In the event of a possible safety signal involving anaphylaxis, the abstraction form could be used to gather the information needed to assess individual cases to see if they meet the Brighton case definition. Since anaphylaxis is an event that could occur with any vaccine the data abstraction form can be used to guide selection of critical criteria needed to meet the case definition, that could then be added to the AEFI report form.

The same data form will also be available online as part of an Automated Brighton Classification (ABC) Tool.

TABLE 5.1 Anaphylaxis KEY CASE DEFINITION CRITERIA AND LIKELY SOURCES OF RELEVANT INFORMATION. Space is also provided to record the actual sources of information.

Criterion	Criterion category	Likely sources of information	Actual sources of information
A	Rapid progression of signs and symptoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immunization clinic notes EMT / ambulance attendant notes Emergency room MD and RN notes Hospital admitting / progress notes Hospital discharge summary Vital signs (Blood pressure, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation) 	
B	Skin symptoms/signs		
C	Cardiac symptoms/signs		
D	Respiratory symptoms/signs		
E	Gastrointestinal symptoms/signs		
F	Mast cell tryptase		Laboratory studies (including orders for mast cell tryptase to be done)

Step 1. Complete the case data entry form choosing the most appropriate answer as defined below:

- ‘YES’ means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was present.
- ‘NO’ means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was not present.
- ‘UNKNOWN’ means there was uncertainty in interpreting whether the criterion was present or absent, OR nothing was documented about the criterion.
- Questions regarding criteria marked with an asterisk* must be answered.

Terms with a glossary definition

Criterion	Question	Possible Answers		
A. Rapid Progression of Signs and Symptoms*	Two or more body systems (Skin, Cardiac, Respiratory Gastrointestinal, Lab) involved from the start or one system involved initially, followed by at least one more system within an hour or less after the first hour	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
Criterion B Skin involvement features				
B	1. Angioedema at a location other than the vaccine administration site	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Patient known to have a history of hereditary angioedema	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Urticaria at a location other than vaccine administration site	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Generalized erythema of the skin WITH pruritus	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	5. Generalized erythema of the skin WITHOUT pruritus	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	6. New onset, bilateral, red AND itchy eyes	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
Criterion C: Cardiac involvement features				
C	1. Measured hypotension based on the age-specific definitions below: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If ≥11 years old: Systolic <90mm Hg OR Diastolic <60 mm Hg OR >30% decrease from the person’s baseline systolic Blood Pressure • If <11 years old: Systolic < the sum of: 70mm Hg + 2 times age in years 	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Loss of consciousness NOTE: choose ‘NO’ if the loss of consciousness was brief and self-resolving in nature, as seen in syncope or vasavagal reflex episodes	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN

Criterion D: Respiratory involvement features				
D	1. Expiratory wheeze documented by a healthcare professional, with or without a stethoscope	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Inspiratory stridor documented by a healthcare professional, with or without a stethoscope	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Upper airway swelling, involving the tongue or throat or uvula or larynx, and documented by a healthcare professional	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Measured hypoxia with an oxygen saturation of <80%	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	5. Tachypnoea	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	6. Cyanosis	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	7. Grunting	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	8. Chest wall retractions	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	9. Increased use of accessory respiratory muscles	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	10. New onset of a persistent cough	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	11. New onset of persistent sneezing	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	12. New onset of persistent runny nose (rhinorrhea)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
Criterion E: Gastrointestinal involvement features				
E0.1	Was ≥ 1 of the vaccines given prior to the onset of symptoms an oral vaccine?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
E0.2	Was the vaccinee an infant <12 mos of age? If YES answer E (1 and 2) below. If NO answer E (3 and 4) below.	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
E	1. New onset of 2 or more episodes of vomiting (relevant if vaccinee an infant)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. New onset of 2 or more episodes of diarrhea (relevant if vaccinee an infant)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. New onset of at least 1 episode of vomiting	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. New onset of at least 1 episode of diarrhoea	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
Criterion F: Mast Cell Tryptase				
F0.1	Was mast cell tryptase measured? If YES, answer F1	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
F1 Elevated Mast cell tryptase	Mast cell tryptase elevated above the laboratory upper limit of normal	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN

Step 2. Based on clinical data entered in Step 1, assign a value to each criterion using the rules in the Criterion Options column. NOTE: B1.1, B1.2, D1.1, D1.2, E1.1, E1.2, E2.1 and E2.2 are defined below based on data entered in Step 1; their only purpose is to define B1, D1 and E which, along with A (defined in Step 1), B, C, D2 and F are then used in Steps 3 and 4 to determine level of certainty.

CRITERION					Criterion value: compare data entered in step 1 table to formulae in the YES, NO and UNKNOWN columns to determine FINAL VALUE for each MAJOR and Minor Criterion		
Clinical Category	Name	FINAL VALUE (Circle/Highlight)			YES (Y)	NO (N)	Unknown (U) if
MAJOR Skin - Angioedema	B1.1	Y	N	U	B (1 = YES) AND B (2 = NO or UNKNOWN)	B (1 = NO) OR B (1 AND 2 = YES)	B (1) = UNKNOWN
MAJOR Skin - Other	B1.2	Y	N	U	B (3 OR 4) = YES	B (3 AND 4) = NO	B (3 AND 4) = NO or UNKNOWN*
MAJOR SKIN Present	B1	Y	N	U	B1.1 OR B1.2 = YES	B1.1 AND B1.2 = NO	B1.1 AND B1.2 = UNKNOWN
Minor Skin Present	B2	Y	N	U	B (5 OR 6) = YES	B (5 AND 6) = NO	B (5 AND 6) = NO or UNKNOWN*
MAJOR Cardiac Present	C	Y	N	U	C (1 or 2) = YES	C (1 AND 2) = NO	C (1 AND 2) = NO or UNKNOWN*
Stridor/Wheeze/Upper airway swelling	D1.1	Y	N	U	D (1 or 2 or 3) = YES	D (1 AND 2 AND 3) = NO	D (1 AND 2 AND 3) = NO or UNKNOWN*
Respiratory Distress	D1.2	Y	N	U	≥2 OF D (4, 5, 6, 7, 8 OR 9) = YES	≥5 OF D (4, 5, 6, 7, 8 OR 9) = NO	≥5 OF D (4, 5, 6, 7, 8 OR 9) = NO OR UNKNOWN*
MAJOR Respiratory Present	D1	Y	N	U	D1.1 OR D1.2 = YES	D1.1 AND D1.2 = NO	D1.1 AND D1.2 = UNKNOWN
Minor Respiratory Present	D2	Y	N	U	D (10, 11 or 12) = YES	D (10 AND 11 AND 12) = NO	D (10 AND 11 AND 12) = NO or UNKNOWN*
Vomiting in <12 month old	E1.1	Y	N	U	(E0.1 = NO) AND (E0.2 = YES) AND (E1 = YES)	(E0.1 = YES) OR (E0.2 = YES and E1 = NO)	(E0.1 = UNKNOWN) OR [(E0.2 = YES and E1 = UNKNOWN)]
Diarrhoea in <12 month old	E1.2	Y	N	U	(E0.2 = YES) AND (E2 = YES)	(E0.2 = YES) and (E2 = NO)	(E0.2 = YES) AND (E2 = UNKNOWN)
Vomiting in ≥12 mos old	E2.1	Y	N	U	(E0.1 = NO) AND (E0.2 = NO) AND (E3 = YES)	(E0.1 = YES) OR [(E0.2 = NO) and (E3 = NO)]	(E0.1 = UNKNOWN) OR [(E0.2 = NO) and (E3 = UNKNOWN)]
Diarrhea in ≥12 mos old	E2.2	Y	N	U	(E0.2 = NO) AND (E4 = YES)	(E0.2 = NO) and (E4 = NO)	[E0.2 = NO) and (E4 = UNKNOWN)
Major Gastrointestinal Present	E	Y	N	U	≥1 of (E1.1, E1.2, E2.1 OR E2.2) = YES	(E1.1 AND E1.2) = NO OR (E2.1 AND E2.2) = NO	(E1.1 AND E1.2) = NO or UNKNOWN* OR (E2.1 AND E2.2) = NO or UNKNOWN*
Major Laboratory Present	F	Y	N	U	F1 = YES	F1 = NO	(F0.1 = NO or UNKNOWN) or (F1 = UNKNOWN)

* *NOTE: choose UNKNOWN if there is a combination of NO and unknown with no YES's (e.g., if D (5 + 6) = NO and D(7) = UNKNOWN, D2 = UNKNOWN)*

Step 3. Record the final value for A1 from step 1 above and for B1, B2, C, D1, D2, E and F from step 2 above. Y = YES, N = No, U = Unknown

Criterion	A	B1	B2	C	D1	D2	E	F
Final Value								

Step 4. Use the final values of all anaphylaxis criteria recorded in Step 3 above to determine the level of certainty based on the formulae below. Start with Level 1 (criteria **A, B1, C, D1, E** and **F**). If not met move to Level 2 (criteria **A, B1, C, D1, E** and **F**) and if not met try Level 3 (all criteria). If none of Levels 1, 2 or 3 are met, try Level 5 (all criteria). If Levels 1, 2, 3 and 5 not met, then assign Level 4. (Resp = Respiratory; GI = Gastrointestinal; Lab = Laboratory)

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	(A = YES) AND (B1 = YES) AND (C OR D1 OR E OR F = YES)
Level 2	(A = YES) AND (B1 = NO OR UNKNOWN) AND [≥ 2 of C OR D1 OR E OR F = YES]
Level 3 can be met in three ways	3.1 (A = YES) AND (B1 AND D2 = YES) AND (C AND D1 AND E AND F = NO or UNKNOWN)
	3.2 (A = YES) AND (D1 AND B2 = YES) AND (B1 AND C AND E AND F = NO or UNKNOWN)
	3.3 (A = YES) AND 1 of (C OR E OR F = YES) AND (B2 OR D2 = YES) AND (B1 AND D1 = NO or UNKNOWN)
Level 4	Reported anaphylaxis but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	A = NO OR [(B1 AND C AND D1 AND E AND F = NO)] OR [(B1 = YES) AND (C AND D1 AND E AND F = NO) AND (D2 = NO)] OR [(D1 = YES) AND (B1 AND C AND E AND F = NO) AND (B2 = NO)] OR [(B1 AND D1 = NO) AND (Only 1 of [C OR E OR F = YES] AND (B2 AND D2 = NO)]

Figure 3. Pictorial algorithm for determining anaphylaxis level of diagnostic certainty

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Accessory respiratory muscles	Muscles, primarily in the neck (sternocleidomastoid which elevates sternum; scalene group which elevates upper ribs) which assist but don't play a primary role in breathing. When used at rest they indicate a level of respiratory distress or increased work of breathing.
Angioedema	Areas of deeper swelling of the skin or mucosal tissues which may not be well circumscribed and usually not itchy. NOTE: hereditary angioedema, usually with a history of recurrent episodes of swelling, should be excluded (affects 1 in 50,000)
Bilateral	Involving both right and left sides of the body
Cyanosis	Abnormal bluish-purple colour of the skin seen in disorders where oxygen attached to circulating red blood cells is decreased.
Erythema	Abnormal redness of the skin without any raised skin lesions
Generalized	Involving >1 body site – that is each limb is counted separately as is the abdomen, back, head and neck. Synonym = widespread
Grunting	A sudden and short noise with each breath when breathing out
Hereditary angioedema	A genetically acquired disorder that results in recurrent episodes of severe swelling, typically seen in arms, legs, face, intestinal or respiratory tract.
Hypotension	An abnormally low blood pressure (BP) documented by appropriate measurement. Age dependent as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <11 years: Systolic < the sum of: 70mm Hg + 2 times age in years • ≥11 years: Systolic <90 mm Hg OR Diastolic <60 mm Hg OR > 30% decrease from the person's baseline systolic BP
Hypoxia	Lower than normal levels of oxygen in body tissues.
In-drawing or retractions	Inward movement of the muscles between the ribs (inter-costal), in the lower part of the neck (supra-clavicular or tracheal tug) or below the chest (sub-costal).
Loss of consciousness	Total suspension of conscious relationship with the outside world as demonstrated by an inability to perceive and respond to verbal, visual or painful stimulus
Mast cell tryptase	Inflammatory mediator released by mast cells during acute anaphylaxis. Typically, levels peak between 15 and 120 minutes after onset; samples for measurement should be taken within 6 hours of onset of signs/symptoms.
New onset	Not present prior to the onset of the current episode
Persistent	Recurring or lasting longer than 5 minutes
Pruritus	Itchiness
Red and itchy eyes	Redness of the whites of the eyes (sclera) with sensation that provokes the desire to rub and/or scratch to obtain relief.
Retractions	Indrawing of skin while breathing in (implies an obstruction to breathing); may be supraclavicular (above the collarbone), suprasternal (above the sternum), intercostal (between the ribs), substernal (below the sternum) or subcostal (abdomen just below the rib cage)
Rhinorrhea	Discharge of thin nasal mucus from the nose
Sneezing	An involuntary (reflex), sudden, violent, and audible expulsion of air through the mouth and nose.
Stridor	A harsh and continuous sound made on inspiration (breathing in)
Syncope	Fainting or passing out. Multiple causes but most common in immunization setting is vasovagal syncope – see definition below.
Tachypnoea	Faster than normal respiratory rate. Age (in yrs) specific upper normal limits for breaths/min: <1=60; 1-<2=40; 2-<5=35; 5-<12=30; >12=16
Urticaria (hives)	Localized redness of superficial layers of skin that is itchy, raised, sharply demarcated and transient (usually lasts <12 hours)

<p>Vasovagal reflex</p>	<p>The vagus nerve is a cranial nerve originating in the brain. The reflex involves the vagal nerve, peripheral nerves and the heart and blood vessels. The reflex causes a sudden drop in blood pressure and heart rate and may lead to pooling of blood in the legs which adds to the low blood pressure and results in lower blood flow to the brain. Common stimuli that lead to the reflex include emotional stress or fear which may be the result of anxiety at the time of being immunized.</p>
<p>Wheeze</p>	<p>A whistling, squeaking, musical or puffing sound made on expiration (breathing out).</p>

APPENDIX 6

Methodology: Brief Summary

6.1. Anaphylaxis ICD-9/10-CM and MedDRA Codes[2-6]

An initial set of codes were retrieved through the Codemapper tool that was developed in the IMI-ADVANCE project. Subsequently they were reviewed and classified into narrow or broad codes by the authors.

CodeMapper[2] builds upon information from the Metathesaurus of the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS). The **Metathesaurus** is a compendium of many medical vocabularies, which have been integrated by assigning equivalent codes and terms from different source vocabularies to the same concepts. Each concept in the UMLS is identified by a CUI. A CUI is a Concept Unique Identifier for a Metathesaurus concept to which strings with the same meaning are linked. The Metathesaurus contains more than one million concepts connected to codes from 201 vocabularies. Each concept is assigned to one or more of 127 semantic types, which define broad conceptual categories like Disease or syndrome, Finding, or Substance. [3] Codemapper was built on the version 2016AA of the UMLS. The automatic concept identification of CodeMapper is based on lexical information from the Metathesaurus. The lexical information of a concept consists of terms that can be used in free text to refer to that concept. We compiled a dictionary for the concepts in the semantic groups Anatomy, Chemicals & Drugs, Disorders, Genes & Molecular Sequences, Living Beings, Phenomena, Physiology, and Procedures of non-suppressible, English terms from several vocabularies including ICD-9 CM, ICD-10 CM, and MedDRA. [4, 5] A text-indexing engine Peregrine uses this dictionary to identify medical concepts in the case definition.[6] Of note, while SPEAC focused on ICD-9/10-CM, MedDRA and SNOMEDCT codes, the CodeMapper concepts shown in the table can be used to search for codes in other systems including MeSH, ICPC-2 and Read-CTv3.

CodeMapper has three screens.

1. The first displays the free text entered by the user – in this case the Brighton case definition. Medical concepts are automatically identified in the text and highlighted inline.
2. The second displays the mapping as a table with one row for each medical concept, and one column for each targeted vocabulary. Each cell contains the names of the codes that are used to represent the medical concept of the row in the targeted vocabulary of the column. The codes are displayed when the names are hovered over with the mouse. Several user operations are available for revising the mapping. The user can remove concepts from the mapping, search and add concepts, or retrieve more general and more specific concepts. The retrieved concepts are shown in a list and can be selected by the user for inclusion in the mapping. The user can also add or remove vocabularies that should be targeted by the mapping. After every operation, the codes are automatically updated and displayed in the table.
3. The third shows a list of all operations that have been made, for later traceability of the mapping process. When the user saves the mapping, he has to provide a summary of the modifications, which is incorporated into the mapping history. The user can download the mapping as a spreadsheet file to incorporate the codes into extraction queries. The spreadsheet file comprises the original free-text case definition, the concepts of the mapping, the codes for the targeted vocabulary, and the full history of the mapping process.

Codemapping was conducted by MS. The output of the Codemapper concepts was reviewed by a medical expert (BL) familiar with the Anaphylaxis Brighton case definitions for all Tier 1 AESI. The concepts identified for Anaphylaxis were considered relevant for background incidence rate determination as well as to study hypotheses related to Anaphylaxis as a vaccine-product related reaction.

For a more detailed description of methodology see [SO2-D2.3 Tier 1 AESI: ICD-9/10-CM and MedDRA Codes](#) which is available in the CEPI Developers' Toolbox and at the [Brighton Collaboration website](#).

6.2. Anaphylaxis Background Incidence

What follows is the methodology used for V1.0 of the Companion Guide. It is kept here because most of the references found in that search have been kept for this guide. Details of the search done for the updated background incidence are provided in the Methods section on page 7.

A systematic literature search to estimate the incidence of acute Anaphylaxis in the population was conducted using the following search strategy:

("Anaphylaxis"[Mesh:noexp] OR "anaphylaxis"[ti] OR "anaphylactic"[ti]) AND ("Incidence"[Mesh:noexp] OR "incidence"[tiab]) AND English[lang] AND ("2000/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT]) AND ("Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type] NOT ("animals"[Mesh:noexp] NOT "humans"[Mesh:noexp])) NOT ("Coronavirus"[Mesh:noexp] OR "coronavirus"[ti] OR "nCoV"[ti] OR "COVID"[ti] OR "SARS-CoV-2"[ti]) NOT ("therapy"[ti] OR "therapies"[ti] OR "therapeutic"[ti] OR "treatment"[ti] OR "treatments"[ti] OR "drug"[ti] OR "drugs"[ti] OR "trial"[ti] OR "trials"[ti] OR "prevention"[ti] OR "prevent"[ti] OR "prevents"[ti] OR "surgery"[ti] OR "procedure"[ti] OR "procedures"[ti]).

Articles had to meet the following criteria:

1. Original research/meta-analysis
2. Population-based study (selecting the entire population or using probability-based sampling methods)
3. Reported an incidence estimate (or raw numbers that allowed the calculation of an estimate).

If multiple articles reported data from the same study population, the most comprehensive data were used. When studies reported on different data collection years or subgroups (sex, age), efforts to include all nonoverlapping data were made. Age, sex, study location, sources of ascertainment, and definitions/diagnostic criteria for Anaphylaxis were extracted. Anaphylaxis incidence estimates, raw numbers, and confidence intervals (CIs) (when provided) were recorded along with any stratified results by age, sex, or year of data collection.

Articles were screened by a single medical reviewer (BL). Screened in articles were reviewed and relevant data abstracted for inclusion in the background rate table (MRV) when novel articles were found from systematic reviews, these were included. The spreadsheet with all extracted background incidence data is available on the [Brighton Collaboration website](#).

6.3. Anaphylaxis Risk Factors[1, 68-70, 72-74, 84, 85, 93]

What follows is the methodology used for V1.0 of the Companion Guide. It is kept here because most of the references found in that search have been kept for this guide. Details of the search done for the updated background incidence are provided in the Methods section on page 7.

A risk factor is “an exposure, behavior, or attribute that, if present and active, clearly alters the occurrence of a particular disease compared with an otherwise similar group of people who lack the risk factor”. According to James Last dictionary of epidemiology version 4, a risk factor is an aspect of personal behavior or lifestyle, an environmental exposure, or an inborn or inherited characteristic, that, on the basis of epidemiologic evidence, is known to be associated with health-related condition(s) considered important to prevent. The term risk factor is rather loosely used, with any of the following meanings:

1. An attribute or exposure that is associated with an increased probability of a specified outcome, such as the occurrence of a disease. Not necessarily a causal factor. A RISK MARKER.
2. An attribute or exposure that increases the probability of occurrence of disease or another specified outcome. A DETERMINANT.
3. A determinant that can be modified by intervention, thereby reducing the probability of occurrence of disease or other specified outcomes. To avoid confusion, it may be referred to as a modifiable risk factor.

Risk factors can include infection, medication, diet, surgical or medical procedure, environmental location, stress, toxins, trauma and vaccine. Attribute includes genetic makeup, age, gender, ethnicity, social status, occupation. Behavior includes smoking, drinking, other substance abuse, sexual practices, level of physical activity. A standard tabular format, as shown in the appendices was used to summarize the key known risk factors for each AESI. Risk factors are only included if there is evidence for an association with the AESI.

The published Brighton Case definition[1] for Anaphylaxis was reviewed for evidence related to associated risk factors. In addition, review articles published after the Brighton case definition were retrieved and reviewed in depth regarding known risk factors for acute Anaphylaxis.[68-70, 72-74, 84, 85, 93]

6.4. Anaphylaxis Case Definition key caveats for diagnosis, data analysis and presentation[1, 198]

The published Brighton case definition for Anaphylaxis[1] and a follow-up publication on using the case definition[198] were reviewed and key aspects identified with particular relevance to real time assessment of Anaphylaxis in the context of a clinical trial where it occurs as an AEFI. In addition, the guideline section of the published Anaphylaxis case definition was reviewed, and key recommendations identified for data collection, analysis and presentation.

For a more detailed description of methodology see [SO1-D2.7 Guidance for CEPI Developers](#) which is available in the CEPI Developers' Toolbox.

6.5. Data Abstraction & Interpretation Form, Tabular Checklist and Algorithms for Level of Certainty Determination

The revised Brighton case definition for anaphylaxis[2] was thoroughly and repeatedly reviewed by one individual (BL) identify all clinical, laboratory and other criteria (e.g., temporal course of disease) used to define each and every case definition level of certainty.

A data abstraction form was developed to capture information relevant to the revised Anaphylaxis case definition criteria. The form uses a standard format developed to ensure harmonized approaches between paper forms (as here in the Companion Guide) and digital forms used online. The questions in the form are designed to enable one of three possible answers:

- 'YES' means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was present.
- 'NO' means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was absent or not present.
- 'UNKNOWN' means there was uncertainty in interpreting whether the criterion was present or absent OR nothing was documented about the criterion

Step 1 involves completing the data abstraction form. Most of the criteria used to determine level of diagnostic certainty (LOC) are determined by the evidence provided in Step 1. However, for some criteria further manipulation of the data entered in Step 1 is needed to define one or more specific criteria. This is done in Step 2. A small summary table of all the final criterion values from the first two steps is done as Step 3. Step 4 involves a tabular algorithm that uses the values of the Case Definition Criteria (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) to determine the highest achievable LOC with Level 1 being the highest, most specific level (Definite Case). A one-page pictorial algorithm is created to show the stepwise pathway to each defined LOC based on the criterion values. This algorithm is designed for use as a stand-alone tool for LOC calculation since in addition to the pathway it also defines the data needed for each criterion.

A glossary of terms relevant to the case definition criteria was developed based initially on the published case definition. Where possible, the term definition was taken directly from the published case definition (often from the footnotes

provided within each published case definition). If there was no definition in the Brighton publication, then an online search was done to obtain definitions based on available medical dictionaries or other on-line resources. The glossary is provided for use by data-abstractors without a medical background.

APPENDIX 7

Changes in the 2022 Anaphylaxis case definition relative to the first version published in 2007

Appendix 7 – Changes in the 2022 Anaphylaxis case definition relative to the first version published in 2007

Brighton Collaboration published the Anaphylaxis case definition in 2007[1] and a Companion Guide, structured as noted above, was first prepared for Anaphylaxis in February 2021. In June 2021 a working group was formed to review and revise the Anaphylaxis case definition in response to a long-standing issue with double-counting lip swelling as both a dermatologic and respiratory major criterion as well to new issues with application of the case definition during the COVID-19 mass vaccination campaigns. The issues are fully described in the newly published case definition[2] and won't be repeated here. Throughout the guide, the 2007 version will be referred to as Anaphylaxis V-1 and the updated version as Anaphylaxis V-2. The key changes from V-1 to V-2 are summarized below:

- Removal of the requirement for sudden onset of signs and symptoms – which was never defined in V-1
- Retention of the need for rapid progression of signs and symptoms AND provision of a definition of rapid progression (not included in V-1) as follows: typically, anaphylaxis onset involves symptoms or signs from multiple body systems (skin, mucosa, respiratory, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal) at the same time; the criterion can also be met if there is ≤ 1 hour from onset involving one body system to involvement of one or more additional body systems.
- **Major skin criteria:**
 - Both 'urticaria' and 'angioedema' retained as major criteria but no longer described as 'generalized' and must be at a location other than the vaccine administration site
 - Generalized erythema and generalized pruritus with skin rash detailed in V-1 have been combined in V-2 into a single major criterion: generalized erythema of the skin with itch.
- **Minor skin criteria:**
 - The following three V-1 criteria have been deleted: generalized pruritus without skin rash; generalized prickle sensation; localized injection site urticaria
 - Red and itchy eyes have been retained as a criterion in V-2 with the added requirement that it be bilateral and of new onset
 - V-2 includes a new minor criterion: generalized erythema of the skin without itch
- **Major respiratory criteria**
 - Wheeze and Stridor have been retained as major criteria but further defined as 'Expiratory wheeze' and 'Inspiratory stridor' and both with the requirement to be documented by a healthcare professional (with or without a stethoscope)
 - Upper airway swelling is retained as a major criterion with the notable difference that lip swelling is no longer included; it still includes swelling of the tongue, pharynx, uvula or larynx but adds the requirement that whatever is present be unequivocally documented by a healthcare profession. Notably this means that they are objective findings as opposed to subjective reporting from a patient.
 - V-2 retains the five indicators of respiratory distress, mentioned in V-1 (tachypnoea, cyanosis, grunting, chest wall retractions, increased use of accessory respiratory muscles) and adds a sixth: measured hypoxia with oxygen saturation $< 90\%$. The presence for two or more indicators of respiratory distress being required to meet this major criterion remains unchanged,
- **Minor respiratory criteria**
 - Two subjective minor criteria in V-1 have been removed: difficulty breathing without wheeze or stridor; and sensation of throat closure.
 - Hoarse voice, a minor criteria in V-1, has been removed.
 - Persistent dry cough, sneezing and rhinorrhea have been retained but have been reduced to a single minor criterion as follows: cough and/or sneezing and/or runny nose that is new onset and persistent.
- **Major cardiac criteria:**
 - Measured hypotension remains unchanged from V-1
 - Clinical features of uncompensated shock have been removed as major criteria.

- Loss of consciousness, one of five possible indicators of uncompensated shock in V-1, is now included as a major criterion with an added caveat that it does not include the 'brief, self-resolving loss of consciousness typical of a vasovagal reaction'.
- **Minor cardiac criteria:**
 - No minor cardiac criteria are included. The single minor criterion from V-1 (reduced peripheral circulation) has been omitted.
- **Gastrointestinal Criteria**
 - Diarrhea and vomiting, previously minor criteria in V-1, have been included as major criteria with three caveats:
 - Either must be of new onset
 - For infants <12 months old, there must be two or more episodes.
 - Neither criterion apply to a setting involving an orally administered vaccine; Must be either injected or intranasal vaccine to include the gastrointestinal major criterion.
 - The four minor gastrointestinal criteria in V-1 have been removed.
- **Laboratory Criterion**
 - An elevated tryptase, included as a minor criterion in V-1, has been included as a major criterion with guidance on the extent of the elevation: \geq upper normal limit for laboratory doing the test, OR $1.2 \times$ baseline tryptase + 2 ng/L.
- **Levels of certainty (LoC):** In general, V-2 is more restrictive than V-1 in terms of the requirements to meet a LoC. Major criteria from at least one system need to be met to reach any LoC with the additional specifications for each Level as follows:
 - **Level 1:** Major criteria from skin and mucosa and from any another system (respiratory, cardiac, gastrointestinal or laboratory) must be met.
 - **Level 2:** Major criteria from two different systems including respiratory and/or cardiac and/or gastrointestinal and/or laboratory should be met. Skin and mucosa are excluded since, if present, this would meet a LoC 1.
 - **Level 3:** Major criteria from one system required plus a minor from a different system (skin/mucosa and/or respiratory systems).

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